

AI-EmpaTe

HANDBOOK ON THE BEST PRACTICES ON AI USE

VOLUME I

Handbook on the Best Practices on AI Use

Volume I

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Handbook on the Best Practices on AI Use (Volume I) is one of the key outputs of the Erasmus+ KA220 HED project AI-EmpaTe (AI Empowered Teaching: Unlocking the Future of Digital Education for Teachers), which aims to enhance AI literacy and foster pedagogical innovation among both pre-service and in-service teachers across Europe and beyond. Focusing on Latvia, Israel, the Czech Republic and Slovakia, this volume provides an in-depth examination of national education systems, policy frameworks, teacher education structures and emerging practices related to the integration of AI in education.

Volume I addresses a critical gap between educational policy and classroom application, offering insights into both government-led strategies and grassroots initiatives that shape AI-enhanced learning environments. It analyses how AI is being embedded at all levels of education, from early childhood through to higher education, while also reviewing current reforms, teacher standards and institutional responses. A central component of the handbook is the AI Literacy Framework, developed by the project partners, which outlines core competencies for the ethical and effective use of AI in teaching and learning.

Although the potential of AI in education is widely acknowledged, this report highlights enduring challenges such as uneven access to technology, limited teacher preparedness, infrastructure gaps and regulatory uncertainty. However, a range of promising practices, pilot projects and partnerships between universities, schools and the technology sector are helping to establish a more inclusive and future-oriented educational environment.

By synthesising developments across participating countries, this volume offers practical recommendations for policymakers, educators and researchers. It calls for sustained professional development, stronger ethical oversight and more structured cross-sector collaboration to ensure that AI is not only implemented effectively but also in ways that uphold the fundamental values of education.

About the Project

Project Title: AI-Empowered Teaching: Unlocking the Future of Digital Education for Teachers (AI-EmpaTe)

Project Code: 2024-1-LV01-KA220-HED-000250857

Project Summary

AI-EmpaTe, an Erasmus+ KA220-HED project, aims to equip pre-service teachers and in-service teachers in primary and secondary education with the fundamental knowledge, skills, and competences needed to integrate AI as teaching content in education. The project will develop an open online course to support pre-service and in-service teachers in planning, preparing, and implementing AI-supported instructional practices.

Key Objectives

- Develop AI literacy among pre-service and in-service teachers
- Design an Open Online Course for AI in education.
- Create a handbook on best AI teaching practices.
- Pilot an AI education framework with pre-service and in-service teachers.
- Provide policy recommendations for ethical AI integration.

Core Activities

- **Handbook on AI Best Practices Volume I:** A reference guide for policymakers, researchers, educators, and other stakeholders involved in the integration of AI in education.
- **Handbook on AI Best Practices Volume II:** A practical guide for pre-service and in-service teachers on implementing AI in educational settings.
- **Open Online Course:** Covering AI concepts, integration strategies, ethics, and practical applications.
- **Pilot Testing:** Engaging 80 teacher education students and 80 school teachers.
- **Resource Development:** 8 video tutorials, an AI evaluation framework, and policy recommendations.

Broader Implications

- Dissemination through webinars, publications, and collaboration with policymakers.
- Strengthening cross-national university-school partnerships to bridge research, training, and practice.

Project Partners

- University of Latvia (Latvia) - Coordinator
- Tel Aviv University (Israel)
- Charles University (Czech Republic)
- Matej Bel University in Banská Bystrica (Slovakia)

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CHAPTER 1

THE CURRENT STATE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN EDUCATION: FROM K–12 TO HIGHER EDUCATION

This chapter provides an overview of the current state of Artificial Intelligence (AI) integration in education across four countries: Latvia, Israel, the Czech Republic, and Slovakia. Its primary aim is to offer a factual and up-to-date account of how AI is being adopted within each national education system. Particular attention is given to national and regional policies that support the use of AI in teaching, learning, and teacher education, including efforts to embed AI within curricula and everyday educational practice. Each country section considers not only technological developments, but also the wider societal, political, and educational conditions shaping AI integration, such as governmental strategies, cultural factors, and implementation challenges. Together, the four profiles provide comparative insight into how different contexts influence the uptake and use of AI in education.

A secondary aim of the chapter is to examine the mechanisms and factors that enable or constrain AI adoption at national, organisational, and individual (teacher) levels. Identifying these mechanisms can inform evidence-based decisions on AI-related policy and practice across the education continuum, from kindergarten to higher education. Drawing on policy implementation models (Matland, 1995; Mthethwa, 2012), the chapter addresses the following questions:

1. What is the primary approach to AI policy implementation in the four countries (top-down, bottom-up, or hybrid), and to what extent is there a feedback loop between policy implementers and field practitioners? How is AI in education being promoted at the national level within and across countries, and how is policy being implemented across different education levels?
2. To what extent are mechanisms in place to embed AI policy in education? What established structures can implementation build upon, and how far do existing mechanisms address critical areas in AI policy development and implementation?
3. What critical areas require further attention to strengthen AI policy development and implementation?
4. What national-level actions are needed to further promote and implement AI in education?

1.1 LATVIA

Latvia's education system is undergoing wide ranging reforms aimed at building a modern, inclusive, and digitally capable learning environment. Skola2030 is a central national initiative supporting a competency-based curriculum that strengthens learners' critical thinking, problem solving, and digital literacy. These reforms are reinforced by strategic policy frameworks, including the Latvian Digital Transformation Guidelines 2021–2027 and the AI Strategy 2020–2025, which emphasise the purposeful integration of advanced digital technologies, including AI, into teaching and learning. Alignment with European Union priorities and funding instruments further supports innovation and systemic change, positioning digital competence and AI-related readiness as key national education priorities. In this section, AI is used as an umbrella term, while GenAI refers specifically to generative systems used for content creation.

On 6 March 2025, the Saeima (the Parliament of Latvia) adopted the Artificial Intelligence Centre Law, establishing a national centre intended to consolidate expertise and resources across the public sector, private sector, and universities. The Centre's objectives include promoting innovation and cross sector partnerships, strengthening public AI skills and equality of access, and ensuring that AI systems are used ethically, responsibly, and safely, with due regard for fundamental rights. The law also highlights a specific national priority by mandating support for the inclusion and sustainability of the Latvian language within AI systems. This emphasis is especially relevant for education because language coverage affects both access to AI tools and the quality of AI mediated learning materials in Latvian.

1.1.1 Overview of Latvia's Education System

Latvia's education system follows the International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED) and includes pre primary, primary, lower secondary, upper secondary, and higher education. Across these levels, digitalisation and informatics are increasingly emphasised to meet the needs of a technology-driven society. In addition, AI-related discussions are increasingly framed around learner digital agency and critical evaluation, not only tool use, reflecting a shift from adoption to responsible integration.

Pre-primary education (ISCED 0)

Pre-primary education lays the foundation for lifelong learning by fostering curiosity, creativity, and early competencies. Age-appropriate use of technology supports the development of initial digital awareness and basic digital skills. At this stage, responsible practice is typically framed as guided exploration and safe digital habits rather than independent AI use.

Primary and lower secondary education (ISCED 1–2)

At these levels, students further develop foundational skills while being progressively introduced to informatics and critical thinking. Latvia's digital transformation agenda is reflected in routine engagement with digital tools and learning resources. The Latvian Digital Transformation Guidelines 2021–2027 highlight digital competencies such as information technology skills and digital literacy as essential for participation in a globally connected economy (Ministry of Economics of the Republic of Latvia, 2020). As GenAI becomes more visible in society, schools increasingly face a practical need to address verification, misinformation risks, and appropriate support for learning, even when AI is not explicitly listed as a separate curriculum topic.

Upper secondary education (ISCED 3)

Upper secondary education builds more targeted competencies, including the use of advanced digital tools and informatics. Skola2030, implemented through national curriculum reform, embeds 21st-century skills in subject learning. Students are expected not only to use digital resources but also to evaluate digital information critically and to create digital outputs that support further study or entry into the labour market. This stage is also where academic integrity expectations become more consequential, as learners produce more extended written work and project outputs that may be influenced by GenAI tools.

Higher education (ISCED 5–8)

Latvia's higher education institutions continue to advance digitalisation, with growing attention to AI and GenAI. Universities, including the University of Latvia and Riga Technical University, offer programmes that combine strong theoretical foundations with applied learning. Riga Technical University, for example, has used EU-supported initiatives to expand AI-learning opportunities across engineering, the sciences, and the social sciences (Riga Technical University, 2022). Increasingly, these programmes address not only practical applications and innovation, but also the ethical and responsible use of AI in academic and

professional contexts. Across higher education, a key implementation challenge is ensuring consistent guidance across faculties and courses so that expectations about AI use, acknowledgement, and assessment are predictable for students.

1.1.2 Policy Framework for Artificial Intelligence in Latvia's Education System

AI integration in Latvia's education system is shaped by both national and European policy directions. The Latvian AI Strategy 2020–2025 highlights data literacy, ethical AI, and digital transformation across sectors, including education (Ministry of Economics of the Republic of Latvia, 2020). This aligns with the European Commission's Digital Education Action Plan 2021–2027, which promotes digital competence development and the strategic use of AI in education (European Commission, 2020).

Latvia also references EU-level ethical guidance for the responsible use of AI and data in education, with emphasis on privacy, transparency, and equitable access (European Commission, 2022). At national level, compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) provides a baseline for protecting learner data, while ethical principles aim to promote trust among educators, students, and stakeholders. However, as AI-enabled services evolve quickly, there is a growing need to translate general data protection principles into practical school and university level procedures, such as guidance on platform selection, data minimisation, and safe classroom use.

Work to conceptualise AI-related competencies across education levels is ongoing, with recurring emphasis on:

- Critical evaluation, assessing accuracy, bias, and reliability of AI generated outputs
- Ethical awareness, recognising ethical implications of AI supported decisions and content creation
- Practical application, using AI tools meaningfully in diverse learning contexts
- Transparency and acknowledgement, clarifying when and how AI support should be disclosed in student work and professional outputs

In higher education, the University of Latvia (LU) and Riga Stradiņš University (RSU) are among institutions advancing specialised and interdisciplinary AI-related learning opportunities (Kalniņa, Nīmante, & Baranova, 2024). Both universities have also introduced recommendations for responsible use of AI in academic work. LU permits AI use in coursework when it is appropriately acknowledged and academic integrity is maintained (University of Latvia, 2024). RSU offers similar guidance with particular attention to ethical

use and copyright considerations (Riga Stradiņš University, 2024). A key implication for policy implementation is the need to align institutional guidance with course level assessment design, so that students are assessed on learning outcomes that remain meaningful in AI rich contexts.

Several institutions contribute to policy coordination and implementation. The Ministry of Education and Science (IZM) and the State Education Development Agency (VIAA) play central roles, supported by partnerships with organisations such as the Latvian Information and Communication Technology Association (LIKTA) and private-sector technology providers that support innovation and access to tools (LIKTA, 2023). These partnerships can accelerate implementation, yet they also require clear quality assurance and ethical procurement principles to avoid uneven adoption and fragmented tool ecosystems across schools.

1.1.3 AI in Curriculum: AI Knowledge and GenAI Literacy

The integration of AI into curriculum and learning continues to expand in Latvia, with initiatives aimed at building both foundational AI awareness and GenAI literacy across educational stages.

To support equitable access to digital learning, an intersectoral memorandum titled “A Computer for Every Child” was signed in 2021, following an initiative by the President of Latvia. With support from the EU Recovery Fund, a laptop provision programme was launched to support socially disadvantaged learners. Such infrastructure measures are an enabling condition for AI-related readiness, but they need to be paired with sustained support for teacher capacity and school level implementation.

AI as a standalone topic

AI is gradually being introduced through pilot initiatives and targeted learning activities that demonstrate relevance to K–12 education. In such initiatives, learners may engage with AI tools for tasks such as language learning and creative writing. These projects are supported through a combination of state funding and private-sector investment, often linked to teacher training. Latvia has also used internationally developed materials translated into Latvian, including Experience AI, developed by the Raspberry Pi Foundation and Google DeepMind. Standalone AI activities can function as entry points, yet their long-term impact depends on integration into subject aims and assessment practices rather than remaining isolated “innovation lessons.”

Integration of AI across disciplines

Alongside standalone approaches, AI-related literacy is increasingly embedded across subjects. In K–12 contexts, students may use GenAI tools (e.g., for drafting, idea generation, or feedback) in ways that support creativity and reflective learning. At the same time, there is growing interest in AI-supported systems that can reduce routine workload (e.g., automated feedback prototypes), allowing teachers to focus on deeper pedagogical work. From an implementation perspective, cross-curricular use requires clear norms about accuracy checking, source evaluation, and the pedagogical purpose of AI support, so that tool use does not replace learning processes such as planning, revision, and reasoning.

In higher education, programmes increasingly explore AI’s ethical, social, and applied dimensions, enabling students to use AI tools across fields from engineering to the social sciences and to reflect on AI’s limitations and risks.

Methodological support materials are also being developed for teachers across subjects through cooperation between VIAA, universities, and professional teacher associations. A key requirement in these materials is to include recommendations for the responsible use of AI technologies within the teaching process. To strengthen uptake, these materials can be complemented by short, classroom-ready exemplars that show what responsible GenAI use looks like in specific subjects, age groups, and assessment types.

1.1.4 Pre-service and In-service Teacher Education in Latvia

Teacher education in Latvia follows a structured pathway combining academic study, supervised practice, and qualification requirements. The system is regulated under national education legislation and overseen by IZM, with professional standards and competency expectations supported by VIAA. Increasingly, these frameworks highlight the need for teachers to integrate digital tools and AI responsibly. A practical policy challenge is ensuring that AI literacy is treated as a pedagogical competence, not only as a technical add on.

Teacher education is provided by institutions such as the University of Latvia, Riga Technical University, and Daugavpils University. Programmes combine pedagogy, subject methodology, educational psychology, and practicum experience. The typical pathway takes four to five years and leads to a Bachelor’s or Master’s degree, depending on the intended teaching level.

Alternative routes also exist. Individuals who have completed non-pedagogical higher education programmes may obtain the right to teach by completing additional pedagogy studies. One example is Mācītspēks, developed with reference to the international Teach For All network and adapted to the Latvian context.

Teacher training programmes are certified and quality-assured through national processes involving IZM, VIAA, and accreditation bodies. Recent developments show increased attention to GenAI literacy, including the use of tools such as ChatGPT for lesson planning, feedback, and learning resource development, alongside explicit attention to ethical and social implications. To strengthen implementation, teacher education can benefit from a clearer progression, beginning with foundational understanding and ethical awareness, and moving towards subject specific pedagogy, assessment design, and communication with learners and parents about AI use.

1.1.5 Teacher Professional Development

Latvia provides a range of professional development opportunities for in-service teachers through workshops, short courses, and longer certification programmes. These are offered by universities and private training providers and supported by institutions such as VIAA and the Latvian Education Development Centre (LEDC). A dedicated financial support programme, managed by VIAA, also promotes the development of teachers' digital competencies.

Professional development increasingly includes AI literacy, with particular focus on GenAI tools and their pedagogical use. Training often targets practical classroom applications (e.g., designing learning activities and resources), as well as the responsible use of AI in assessment, communication, and data-informed teaching. A continuing gap is the availability of sustained, practice-based professional learning that includes follow up, peer exchange, and evidence of impact on teaching and learning, rather than one-off exposure to tools.

1.1.6 Innovative Initiatives in Education and AI

AI adoption in Latvian education is developing through both state led initiatives and grassroots activity. National digitalisation strategies provide a policy foundation for experimentation, including growing interest in adaptive learning approaches and tools that may improve teaching efficiency. At the same time, teachers and schools are increasingly exploring AI tools independently through peer learning, workshops, and practitioner communities, often

motivated by the need to better tailor learning support and reduce administrative workload. This pattern suggests a hybrid implementation trajectory, where policy enables the conditions for adoption while practice communities shape day-to-day interpretation and classroom norms.

Several national events have also strengthened professional dialogue about AI in education. The Mārupe seminar, for example, offered practical guidance for classroom implementation while also addressing potential benefits and limitations (Mārupe State Gymnasium, 2023). The conference *Idea Day: Artificial Intelligence in Education*, organised by the Ministry of Education and Science, focused on governance and regulation and signalled institutional commitment to ethical AI practices (Ministry of Education and Science, 2025). Public lectures such as *Artificial Intelligence: Separating Hype from Reality* have further supported critical engagement among educators (Mislēvičs, 2023). Such events contribute to awareness and agenda setting, but their effectiveness increases when connected to concrete implementation supports, such as guidance documents, exemplar tasks, and structured professional learning pathways.

1.1.7 Local Challenges, Opportunities, and Barriers

Despite notable progress, Latvia faces several challenges in scaling AI integration. Key barriers include uneven infrastructure, limited access to AI tools in some regions, and inconsistent teacher preparation for AI-related pedagogies. Differences between urban and rural contexts may affect equitable access to AI resources. Additional concerns relate to the cost of tools, the need for standardised training pathways, and risks associated with privacy, misinformation, and algorithmic bias. In addition, the rapid evolution of commercial GenAI services creates uncertainty for schools about what platforms are appropriate and how to align their use with safeguarding expectations.

At the same time, interest in AI literacy among educators and students presents an opportunity to modernise teaching and learning. EU funding and public-private partnerships may further accelerate development if aligned with coherent training and safeguarding measures. As noted by the Minister of Education and Science, Melbārde (2025), Latvia is currently in a capacity-building stage, with the intention of later scaling implementation so that a broader population can acquire and understand AI-related competencies.

Latvia is also strengthening its education quality monitoring system. By 2029, plans include developing solutions for monitoring learners' individual performance, with AI supported data processing integrated into the system. This creates an opportunity to improve

responsiveness and support, yet it also raises requirements for transparent governance, clear accountability, and careful data protection practices.

1.1.8 Conclusion

Latvia has demonstrated a clear commitment to integrating AI and digital competencies into education through coordinated reforms and policy development. Initiatives such as Skola2030, the Latvian Digital Transformation Guidelines 2021–2027, and the establishment of the Artificial Intelligence Centre provide strategic direction for embedding 21st century skills and strengthening AI-related readiness across the education system. Growing attention to AI literacy and GenAI use is also reflected in teacher education and professional development, supporting educators in adopting AI in responsible and ethical ways.

While challenges remain, particularly in relation to infrastructure, training capacity, and equitable access, Latvia's alignment with EU priorities and access to European funding mechanisms create favourable conditions for sustained progress. By widening access, strengthening teacher preparation and continuing professional learning, and fostering coordinated collaboration among policymakers, educators, and technology partners, Latvia is well positioned to advance ethical and effective AI integration and to support a digitally empowered and inclusive learning environment. A further step for strengthening implementation is to formalise feedback loops from schools and teacher educators into national guidance, ensuring that policy instruments remain grounded in classroom realities and evolving AI risks.

1.2 ISRAEL

AI is rapidly transforming education globally, and Israel is actively integrating AI-driven tools into its education system. The Israeli Ministry of Education recognises the importance of AI literacy and practical competencies for students and teachers, aligning with global trends in pedagogical innovation, assessment methods, and curriculum development.

A recent policy document (Ministry of Education, 2025) emphasises the need for a structured and ethical AI adoption strategy. This includes classroom integration, AI-based assessment, and regulatory frameworks to ensure responsible usage. These initiatives aim to enhance digital skills, critical thinking, and problem-solving in an AI-driven world. Furthermore, teacher training plays a crucial role in AI implementation, with professional

development programmes focusing on AI literacy, ethics, and innovative teaching practices (Mor & Shapira-Lavi, 2024).

Alongside these advancements in the field, the State Comptroller of Israel report (November, 2024) highlights gaps in infrastructure, teacher preparedness, and regulatory clarity, which must be addressed to ensure equitable access to AI-powered education. By aligning national policies with AI advancements, Israel aims to create an innovative and ethical education system that maximises technology's benefits while addressing pedagogical and social concerns. The coming years will be crucial in determining AI's impact on learning outcomes and educational equity across the country.

1.2.1 Structure of Educational System

The structure of Israel's education system follows the International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED), including pre-primary (ISCED 0, ages 3–6), primary (ISCED 1, grades 1–6, ages 6–12), lower secondary (ISCED 2, grades 7–9, ages 12–15), and upper secondary education (ISCED 3, grades 10–12, ages 15–18). Post-secondary non-tertiary education (ISCED 4) includes vocational and technical programmes, while higher education (ISCED 5–8) comprises undergraduate and postgraduate studies (OECD, 2025).

The Israeli Ministry of Education manages all levels of education, from pre-school to higher education. It sets policies, develops curricula, supervises schools, and promotes science and technology. The Ministry serves both public and private sectors and supports diverse communities, including Jewish, Arab, Druze, and others.

Israel's education system is notably pluralistic in terms of nationality, ethnicity, and religion (Gubernan & Mcdossi, 2023). Among Jewish students, there are distinctions based on ethnicity, immigration background, and religiosity. Due to this diversity, the Ministry is pursuing a teacher education policy that promotes pluralism, aiming to equip teachers for heterogeneous classrooms and to foster mutual understanding and improved outcomes for disadvantaged groups (Yogev, 2021).

In addition to curriculum development and inclusive education, the Ministry oversees teacher training, sets standards and national assessments, supports special education, promotes educational technology, and participates in higher education oversight through funding and quality assurance. Led by the Minister of Education, it works with local authorities, schools, teachers, and parents to implement reforms and enhance educational quality.

1.2.2 Policy Documents

At the Holistic/National level: ethics and regulation

The State of Israel recognises the importance of integrating Generative AI (Gen AI) into education, as highlighted in the State Comptroller's report (November 2024). The report emphasises AI literacy as a core future competency but notes that the education system has yet to be fully integrated into national AI programmes. It recommends that the Ministry of Education and the Ministry of Innovation, Science, and Technology implement AI literacy from an early age.

Following these recommendations, the Israeli Ministry of Education has updated its policy (2025, January 20), emphasising responsible AI use and 21st-century skills. The policy includes AI integration in classrooms, adapting assessments, and ensuring ethical usage. Students using AI tools must reflect on their interaction with AI and design assignments that challenge AI's capabilities. The Institute for Applied AI in Education has outlined a strategic framework for AI education, structured into ten goals across five categories (Mor & Shapira-Lavi, 2024).

Building on these developments in the education system, Israel is advancing and regulating the field of AI through several key initiatives:

- **Ethics and Regulation Principles:** A policy document (Ministry of Education, September 2023) guides government offices on AI regulation, emphasising a sectoral, flexible approach.
- **International Agreement:** Israel signed an international AI regulation agreement, focusing on the public and private sectors (Porter, 2024).
- **Government Knowledge Hub:** A national AI coordination centre was established to oversee regulation, data policy, and ethics (Ministry of Innovation, Science and Technology, 2024).
- **AI Research and Development:** The National AI Programme, backed by multiple ministries, is investing in AI R&D infrastructure, including a National Research Institute for AI to foster academic and industry collaboration. In addition, The Council for Higher Education (CHE) prioritises AI research and academic capacity, expanding university research centres and graduate programmes. The second phase of the programme aims to increase AI-specialised students, promote interdisciplinary research, and foster global collaboration (Ministry of Innovation, Science and Technology, 2024, September 17).

Considerations for the use of AI at different age levels

The Ministry of Education (2023) has tailored AI use policies for different age levels:

Students under 13: AI use is teacher-supervised, follows privacy laws (COPPA, EU standards), and requires parental consent.

Students aged 13-18: Broader independent AI use, provided platforms comply with safety measures, parental consent, and ethical awareness.

Across all ages, teachers encourage discussions on AI risks and ethical challenges, ensuring students develop critical thinking and responsible AI engagement.

A map of the competencies required from students in using AI across different education levels

The Israeli framework for AI competencies outlines a roadmap for equipping students across various educational levels with the necessary skills, knowledge, attitudes, and values to engage with AI effectively and responsibly. The core competencies include Understanding AI mechanisms, Effective AI use, Developing AI agency and Ethical AI engagement. The framework is aligned with Bloom's Taxonomy, national goals, and OECD standards, preparing students for meaningful AI-driven learning.

This framework adapts AI competencies to the unique context of the Israeli educational system, embedding them in progressive educational stages. For primary students, the focus is on building awareness of AI technologies and their applications in everyday life, while fostering curiosity and a basic understanding of ethical considerations. In secondary education, students are introduced to critical evaluation of AI tools, interdisciplinary integration, and scenario-based ethical reasoning. Inspired by Bloom's Taxonomy, the framework ensures a structured progression from basic understanding to creative applications of AI. Designed with adaptability in mind, it aligns with national pedagogical goals and the OECD Learning Compass while emphasising cultural specificity and inclusion. This dynamic and future-ready framework aims to prepare Israeli students for meaningful engagement in an AI-driven world (Filo et al., 2024).

Authorities and institutions that control the quality of education in the country, including the implementation of AI in education

Israel's education system operates through a hierarchical structure in which the Ministry of Education sets policies and oversees schools (Government of Israel, April 2024). The Pedagogical Administration and Secretariat adapt these policies according to different age groups, ensuring their relevance and effectiveness. The Council for Higher Education (CHE, n.d) and the Planning and Budgeting Committee (PBC) are responsible for overseeing universities and shaping higher education policy. Local authorities play a key role in managing school operations, ensuring the smooth implementation of national directives at the regional level. Additionally, the National Authority for Measurement and Evaluation (RAMA, n.d) evaluates the education system's performance, providing data-driven insights for continuous improvement. This coordinated structure facilitates the effective integration of AI in education while maintaining quality control, ethical standards, and alignment with national educational goals.

1.2.3 AI in Curriculum: AI Knowledge and GenAI Literacy

AI knowledge

A national initiative in Israel has recommended introducing AI as a core subject from elementary to high school. It proposes integrating data science and machine learning alongside Hebrew, Mathematics, and English, with basic proficiency required for matriculation and an advanced option available. The curriculum should also cover the ethical issues specific to AI (Ben-Israel et al., 2020).

Currently formal AI education in Israel is primarily available to computer science students through two elective pathways: a 90-hour elective module on machine learning (ML), contributing 30% to the final grade of the track and covering the theory and practice of machine learning, and a comprehensive 450-hour machine learning specialisation within software engineering, offering advanced academic-level instruction and including a hands-on capstone project (Halstuch, 2024). In addition, The Ministry of Education (n.d) has designated Information and Data as a flagship high school subject, introducing AI-based information search. The curriculum covers AI literacy (understanding models, prompts, and AI tools), critical thinking (verifying chatbot responses and evaluating sources), AI ethics (bias, privacy, security, and regulation), and AI-based data analysis (exploring capabilities and limitations of AI tools). Beyond these efforts, blended learning models have been introduced to expand AI

education access for students across all disciplines. These models have proven particularly effective during times of crisis (Perach & Alexandron, 2022).

AI literacy as a part of required general digital competency development

The "National Strategy of Israel" (Ben-Israel et al., 2020) emphasises the importance of integrating AI education into the school system, from kindergarten to high school, at all levels of proficiency. It proposes including AI as a core subject and a cross-disciplinary skill across various fields, with an ethical component to foster ethical awareness and critical thinking. The Ministry of Education (2024, November 13) developed a GenAI competency specification (index) for different age levels. It specifies core skills, and within each core skill, there are basic competencies and optimal competencies detailed according to the target population: Grades 1–2, Grades 3–4, Grades 5–6, Grades 7–9, and Grades 10–12. For teaching staff, management teams, and Ministry of Education headquarters staff, the Ministry defines what each team must know and what they must do in practice for each core skill.

In higher education, there is a recognised emphasis on developing knowledge, skills, and attitudes. This is reflected in the "Academia 360" by the Council for Higher Education (CHE, 2024, April 17), which aims to promote the development of competencies in general, including AI, through deep changes in undergraduate curricula. The programme focuses on promoting the modernisation and innovation of undergraduate programmes, aligning with global trends and emphasising the integration of advanced technologies. One of its primary objectives is incorporating digital components, such as AI, into curricula, thereby encouraging the development of skills tailored to the technological era. Institutions are required to implement innovative teaching methods that integrate AI as a central element and foster 21st-century skills, such as critical thinking and problem-solving, through advanced technological tools. The programme's budget supports institutions in updating at least 20% of their undergraduate programmes or programmes enrolling at least 20% of undergraduate students, while developing new methodologies and integrating advanced digital technologies. This initiative highlights the potential of AI to enhance the learning and teaching experience in academic institutions.

This current policy is reflected at the institutional level. For example, an AI Learning Community, which included over 40 lecturers and partners and was guided and supported by the Teaching and Learning Innovation Deanship team, operated at Tel Aviv University from March to August 2024. Insights from this collaborative learning process were compiled into a

comprehensive report aimed at facilitating the critical and informed integration of generative AI technology into academic teaching. The report addresses the development of GenAI proficiency and literacy among students, as well as the integration of GenAI skills and knowledge into existing university courses (Tel Aviv University, 2024). Similarly, The Holon Institute of Technology (HIT, October 2023) published a position paper emphasising the need for academic institutions to adapt by adopting AI tools, redesigning curricula, and transitioning to active learning approaches such as Project-Based Learning. According to the position paper, as AI reshapes the job market, fostering AI literacy and ethical awareness among students is essential. Educators must receive training to effectively leverage AI, ensuring its benefits are maximised while addressing its challenges.

Integration of AI-based systems

AI systems have not yet been integrated into the official curriculum; however, there are uses of systems that are not part of the curriculum but are incorporated into teaching programmes in various content areas based on the curriculum, on a large scale:

- **PeTeL (Personalised Teaching and Learning)** is an initiative by the Department of Science Teaching at the Weizmann Institute of Science (n.d), aimed at promoting personalised teaching and learning in science and mathematics for middle and high school students in Israel. The platform is based on Moodle and enables teachers to create personalised teaching sequences, integrate interactive content, and receive real-time feedback on student performance. Additionally, PeTeL offers a collaborative repository of diagnostic content and interactive learning materials developed by experts and teachers, supporting personalised teaching and enhancing the learning experience.
- **Albert the Bot** is an AI teaching bot designed to impart AI competencies to students in the education system, aiming for 100% of students and teaching staff to achieve at least a basic level of proficiency. Through games and activities, the bot focuses on developing skills such as creativity, critical thinking, and problem-solving. The learning process consists of seven stages, including selecting a topic, writing a prompt, refining the image created by the bot, and a game to evaluate the acquired knowledge. The initiative incorporates supportive learning videos and encourages reflection to conclude the learning process (Ministry of Education, December 2024).

1.2.4 A System of Pre-Service Teacher Education

Teacher training in Israel typically lasts three to four years, depending on the programme and institution, with shorter retraining programmes of one to two years for career changers (Ministry of Education, 2022; CHE, 2015). Programmes provide both theoretical and practical knowledge, covering lesson planning, classroom management, evaluation methods, educational psychology, and child development. Additionally, students specialise in specific teaching disciplines, such as mathematics, languages, or sciences, while learning subject-specific teaching methodologies (CHE, 2021).

Teacher education takes place in colleges of education and universities, supervised by the Ministry of Education and the Council for Higher Education (CHE). While CHE oversees academic accreditation, the Ministry of Education grants teaching licenses to graduates meeting the academic and practical training requirements (Ministry of Education, 2022; CHE, 2015).

Recent reforms have introduced flexibility in teacher training, allowing institutions to design innovative programmes while maintaining a balance between theory, practice, and digital technologies (Gubernan & Mcdossi, 2023). A major initiative, "Academia-Classroom," expands practical experience, requiring student teachers to spend at least two days per week in schools for co-teaching and hands-on training (Ministry of Education, 2016).

Beyond pedagogy, teacher training also focuses on values education, coexistence, and inclusion, preparing educators for diverse classrooms (CHE, 2021). To attract high-quality candidates, training programmes offer financial incentives, including tuition subsidies and scholarships for those committing to teaching upon graduation. Additionally, specialised programmes aim to train teachers for peripheral regions, addressing unique community needs (Gubernan & Mcdossi, 2023).

A hallmark of Israel's teacher training system is its collaborative approach, involving academic institutions, schools, and the Ministry of Education. These partnerships ensure integrative training, preparing teachers to handle the educational, social, and ethical challenges of modern classrooms (Gubernan & Mcdossi, 2023).

Integration of AI literacy into the curriculum for Pre-service teachers, as well as in teaching and learning practices

A policy paper by “Alumot – Teacher Training in Academia” (2024), operating under the Mofet Institute, presents a policy for integrating technology into the training of new teachers. It emphasises the need to develop digital literacy skills among teachers and suggests adding technological content to the curricula of teacher education colleges. Accordingly On the Mofet Institute website – the National Institute for Research and Development in Teacher Education and Education – an article was published calling for a change in the way teachers are trained in Israel. According to the author, who serves as the head of the Academic Training and CHE-PBC Relations Department, teacher training is the foundation of the entire education system. Therefore, teachers should be trained in a way that reflects how they will actually teach in the classroom – that is, through the use of AI tools (Zeiler & Russo, 2023). For example, as part of a Bachelor’s degree in Education, the College of Management Academic Studies offers courses such as "Learning Strategies in Digital Environments," "Advanced Digital Tools in Education," and "Entrepreneurship and Pedagogical Innovation," focusing on innovative learning technologies and the impact of AI on knowledge and the ethical questions it raises.

1.2.5 Teacher Professional Development

Integration of AI literacy into teacher training programmes

Professional development for teachers in Israel is an ongoing process aimed at enhancing teaching quality, adapting to technological and social changes, and fostering professional identity. It includes training sessions, workshops, and specialised courses in areas such as pedagogy, educational technology, and classroom management. These programmes are offered by academic institutions, Pisga Centres, and schools, using various formats like short-term training (30/60/120 hours), micro-credentialing, and school-based learning (Yozma, 2020; Ministry of Education, 2009; Teachers' Union, n.d.)

The Ministry of Education, the Council for Higher Education, and the Teachers’ Union oversee professional development. The Ministry's Professional Development Division sets policies, develops training programmes, and operates Pisga Centres. The Teachers’ Union, through its Professional Advancement Fund, provides additional training resources (Ministry of Education, 2009).

Professional development focuses on empowering teachers, improving teaching strategies, and promoting innovation. Various initiatives support flexible learning, such as online courses, reading groups, lead teachers, and pedagogical reforms. These efforts align professional development with technological advancements and encourage interdisciplinary collaboration (Yozma, 2020).

The integration of AI in teacher training is increasingly recognised. A study at the Weizmann Institute introduced high school biology teachers to AI-based educational tools, showing that structured exposure boosts confidence in adopting AI in classrooms (Hayak & Eyal, 2023). In line with these results, the Ministry of Education developed a comprehensive AI policy for teacher training, emphasising AI literacy, ethical considerations, and hands-on experience with AI tools (Ministry of Education, n.d.).

Aligned with these efforts, various initiatives highlight the potential of technology to enhance teaching methods and foster innovation. Programmes such as "Entrepreneurship in the Era of AI," provide in-depth training for teachers to develop innovative and entrepreneurial approaches to education using AI tools. Such initiatives aim to promote creativity and pedagogical flexibility among teachers while empowering them to utilise AI technologies to create impactful learning environments. These efforts represent a significant push to modernise the professional development of teachers in Israel and prepare them for an AI-driven educational future (Mofet Institute, n.d.).

1.2.6 Initiatives - Overview of innovative initiatives in education and AI State-led initiatives: Implementation of policies (Top-Down)

Israel is investing significant resources in developing initiatives and projects in the field of AI within the education system, aiming to combine advanced technology with educational values. Moreover, the Ministry of Education in Israel has declared 2025 as the "Year of AI," with the goal of transforming teaching, learning, and educational management. This initiative aims to equip every student and teacher with foundational knowledge of AI tools, integrating them into educational processes to better prepare students for the evolving job market (Government of Israel, 2025, January 7).

- **Teacher Training** - The Ministry of Education (n.d) emphasises the importance of professional development for teachers to effectively integrate AI into education, addressing technological, pedagogical, and social aspects. Training programmes focus on awareness, critical thinking, and practical skills to navigate AI-related challenges. To support this, the

Ministry offers webinars and recorded lectures under "The Edge of Intelligence – Leaders of Innovation and Technology", covering AI applications in creativity, education, music, game development, and workflow optimization. Additionally, the podcast series "Educators with Intelligence" explores AI in Education (AIED), addressing ethical considerations and presenting practical insights from the field, balancing innovation with responsible AI use.

- **Support for ICT coordinators** - Creating a training kit and supporting ICT coordinators to implement AI in educational institutions, while providing tools, guidelines and emphasis on technological, pedagogical and organisational aspects (Ministry of Education, 2024, December 25).
- **Educational practices** - The Ministry of Education (n.d.) publishes practices for integrating AI tools into teaching, learning and assessment, in order to enrich the learning processes and adapt them to the needs of students. The practices include: using AI to create images, assisting in writing texts, developing creative and critical thinking and preparing research papers. In addition, the practices highlight ethical aspects, such as developing an ethical code for the use of AI and evaluating papers based on AI tools.
- **Collaborations with industry** - The Ministry of Education (Government of Israel, 2025, January 7) collaborates with tech leaders like Google, Microsoft, Apple, and Intel to connect education with technology. As part of this effort, the "AI Connect for Education" event, held with Google Israel, introduced teachers and students to generative AI tools for classroom use. Participants received personalised guidance, experimented with Hebrew-adapted tools, and explored ready-to-use AI teaching units, even for those without a technological background.
- **Applied Experiments** - The Institute for Applied Research in AI in Education, established in late 2023 by The Ministry of Education's Innovation and Technology Administration, promotes the responsible and evidence-based use of AI in education. It conducts applied research, publishes best practices, manages a knowledge centre, and leads an international expert community. Key experiments include AI integration in matriculation exams and a "time-saving" study exploring AI's role in reducing teachers' workload, allowing more focus on personalised learning (Ministry of Education, n.d.).
- **AI-Based Assessment** - The National Authority for Measurement and Evaluation (n.d) and the Pedagogical Secretariat provide AI-driven assessment tools for elementary and middle school students. These tools offer immediate skill evaluation, progress reports, and

recommendations in Hebrew, Arabic, and English, focusing on writing, reading comprehension, and fluency. They remain experimental, voluntary, and for internal use only, with no student data collected.

Grassroots initiatives: Bottom-Up applications

The integration of AI into education in Israel is not limited to top-down strategies; it is also driven by grassroots initiatives emerging from the field. Educators, schools, and local organisations are taking the lead in developing innovative approaches to incorporating AI into teaching and learning. These efforts reflect a dynamic and collaborative spirit, aiming to address real-world educational challenges.

Kindergartens

- **“In the Garden of AI”** - A unique project that integrates AI into kindergartens to enhance pedagogical and organisational processes and tailor learning to the needs of children and educational staff (Ministry of Education, n.d.).

Primary and secondary schools

- **Implementation at the municipal level** - For the past two years, the Ramat Gan Municipality has been running a pilot programme developed by Google Israel called "Blossoms of AI" in eight schools in the city. The programme is designed to explain to students the mathematics behind basic AI algorithms at a level appropriate for eighth grade (Ramat Gan Municipality, 2024, August 7).
- **Educational programmes for children and youth** - Private programmes train students in AI literacy, research skills, and practical application, focusing on content identification, ethical use, and integration into learning (Shchakim, n.d.).
- **Teacher Learning Communities on Social Media** - To collaboratively explore knowledge and practices related to AI, discuss them, and learn about their broader impacts, several professional teacher learning communities have been established on social media. One such community is *AI in Education and Academia* (Facebook, n.d.)
- **Developing learning solutions and products** - private initiatives aimed at enabling educators to leverage AI effectively and with ease. For example, a curated database of pre-prepared prompts designed for specific tasks, such as generating content for presentations or crafting assessments for certificates.

Higher education

- **Practices and Tools** - Most higher education institutions in Israel, such as The Open University, Bar-Ilan University and Tel-Aviv University, provide teaching staff with databases of best practices for integrating AI into lessons (Development of learning aids, learning activities and assessment processes), as well as repositories of relevant tools designed for use by both lecturers and students (The Open University of Israel, n.d.; Bar-Ilan University, n.d.; Tel Aviv University, n.d.).
- **TAU virtual tutor** - An AI-based system developed by Tel Aviv University that enables students to engage in a question-and-answer dialogue with a “Virtual Lecturer” outside class hours, using recorded course materials. The initial pilot reported positive outcomes, including high student satisfaction and improved preparedness for lessons. Following this success, the initiative is being expanded to additional courses in the humanities, social sciences, engineering, and the exact sciences (Ynet, 2024, November 3; Reicher et al., 2025).
- **A "Personal Teaching Assistant" chatbot** - The chatbot, powered by the ChatGPT natural language model, was launched by Bar Ilan University. The chatbot has been trained using diverse educational content to support student learning. This tool engages in personalised dialogue with students, adapting to their communication style, and provides detailed responses to academic inquiries. It facilitates discussions on course-related topics, answers questions about the curriculum, and offers practice exercises (Bar-Ilan University, 2024, October 13).
- **Training and conferences-** Meital (The Inter-University Centre for Learning Technologies) provides workshops and seminars on integrating AI tools in education and research. Events include "AI Tools for Research: Perplexity and Elicit" and "GenAI in Higher Education", exploring AI’s impact on academia while maintaining its core values (Centre for Knowledge and Learning Technologies, 2024, March 18).

1.2.7 Local Challenges, Opportunities, and Barriers

The integration of Gen AI in Israel's education system presents both challenges and opportunities, requiring innovative and equitable policies. The State Comptroller's report identifies gaps in infrastructure, teacher training, and AI awareness as key obstacles, exacerbated by the lack of a unified government policy. However, this challenge also creates

opportunities for strategic programmes that could strengthen Israel's position as a global leader in AI education (State Comptroller of Israel, 2024, November).

Research shows that teachers in Israel exhibit relatively high trust in AI technologies but express concerns regarding ethical issues such as privacy, transparency, and the potential impact on social relationships in the classroom. Despite these challenges, teachers with greater familiarity and understanding of AI tend to recognise its capacity to enhance teaching and learning processes, particularly through personalised content and real-time feedback. This highlights the need to invest in teacher training and the development of targeted professional knowledge while building supportive infrastructures (Tel Aviv University, 2024).

Additional findings from the Chief Scientist's report emphasise the importance of integrating AI into education as a means of reducing socioeconomic gaps and providing access to diverse learning resources. By developing accessible technological tools and emphasising ethics and equality, AI can serve as a catalyst for both social and economic growth (Ramiel, June 2023).

Moreover, a report from Tel Aviv University highlights that integrating generative AI in academic teaching enables pedagogical innovation, such as fostering critical and creative thinking skills among students. The report recommends a thoughtful and informed approach to incorporating the technology, addressing its limitations and opportunities while emphasising the importance of training educators for effective use of these tools (Tel-Aviv University, 2024).

Finally, the most significant opportunity lies in Israel's ability to develop a comprehensive educational vision focused on cross-sector collaboration and the promotion of applied research in AI. By emphasising a national strategy, professional training, and the adaptation of digital infrastructures, the education system can maximise the vast potential of AI while empowering teachers and enhancing learning processes for students. In doing so, Israel has the potential to become a global leader in the adoption of technological innovation in education (Ramiel, June 2023).

1.2.8 Conclusion

Israel is in the midst of integrating Gen AI into its education system, focusing on advancing pedagogical innovation and enhancing the learning experience. The successful initiatives and applications demonstrate the immense potential of these technologies to improve teaching quality and prepare the younger generation for the modern world. However, addressing

the ethical and technological challenges associated with AI use is essential to ensure an equitable, ethical, and effective education system for all Israeli students.

1.3 CZECH REPUBLIC

In recent years, the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports (MŠMT) has undertaken a major revision of the national curricular framework through the National Pedagogical Institute of the Czech Republic (NPI ČR). This work covers the Framework Educational Programmes (FEPs) for pre-primary, primary, lower secondary, basic art, and upper secondary education. One of the most significant changes is the introduction of Informatics as a compulsory subject across primary, lower secondary, and upper secondary levels. From the 2024/25 school year, Informatics becomes mandatory and, for many schools, an entirely new subject.

Across educational stages, the Informatics curriculum is structured around four core thematic units: Data, Information, and Modelling; Algorithms and Programming; Information Systems; and Digital Technologies. In parallel, the revised FEPs also strengthen expectations that digital competence is developed across all grades and educational areas.

Implementation of the revised FEP for basic schools (primary and lower secondary) is planned as a phased rollout: September 2025 as an optional start for Grades 1 and 6, September 2027 as a mandatory start for Grades 1 and 6, and September 2031 as mandatory implementation across all grades. This staged approach is intended to give schools sufficient time to adapt curricula, learning resources, and teacher capacity.

A persistent challenge in the Czech education system is the strong relationship between students' educational outcomes and socio-economic background. International large-scale assessments, including ICILS and PIRLS, indicate above average differences in student performance associated with socio-economic factors. Reading outcomes among Czech pupils in Year 4, as measured in PIRLS, have not improved substantially over the past two decades, and there has been a slight increase in the proportion of pupils performing below the lowest proficiency levels. Against this backdrop, the Czech Republic launched the national initiative Innovation in education in the context of digitisation in 2022 within the Recovery and Resilience Plan, aligned with longer term national and European strategies and spanning pre-primary to upper secondary education for learners aged 3 to 18 (OECD, 2023, p. 200).

1.3.1 Structure of Educational System

The Czech education system supports learners across all levels, following the ISCED framework. It encompasses pre-primary (ISCED 0) for ages 3-6, primary (ISCED 1) for ages 6-11 covering grades 1-5, lower secondary (ISCED 2) for ages 11-15 covering grades 6-9, upper secondary (ISCED 3) for ages 15-19 covering grades 1-4, and higher education (ISCED 4-7), with a strong emphasis on digital competences and informatics education.

The majority of kindergartens (91.7%), primary (92.9%) and secondary schools (73.6%) are public. Education at public schools in the Czech Republic is free of charge. Compulsory education in the Czech Republic lasts from the age of 5 to 15 for a total of 10 years which is below the OECD average of 11 years (OECD, 2024).

Pre-school education (ISCED 0)

Preschool education (ISCED 0) is mainly provided in kindergartens for children from 3 to 6 years of age. The last year of pre-primary education is compulsory. Activities for the development of children's computational thinking (CT) have been included in the FEP for pre-primary education; these activities are carried out in the form of CSUnplugged or with interactive touch surfaces or robotic toys.

Basic school education (ISCED 1-2)

Basic education is divided into two stages: primary education (ISCED 1, five years) and lower-secondary education (ISCED 2, four years). A notable system-level issue is the high rate of postponed school entry: up to 20% of children begin primary school at age seven rather than six.

As the revised FEPs are introduced, compulsory informatics has been incorporated into primary schooling and is being extended across lower-secondary education. However, there is a shortage of qualified informatics teachers. Approximately 60.4% of basic schools do not have certified informatics teachers. While overall teaching qualification levels averaged 76.0% in 2022/23, informatics is among the subjects with the most frequent qualification gaps, particularly in areas such as coding, algorithms, and programming, which can be difficult to teach without dedicated preparation.

Upper secondary schools (ISCED 3)

Secondary education (ISCED3) in the Czech Republic is provided by upper secondary schools (grammar schools - the so-called gymnasium - with the Maturita exam; secondary vocational schools with a CET certificate; secondary vocational schools) and conservatoires. Admission to study is conditional on the completion of compulsory school attendance and compliance with the conditions of the admission procedure. 75% of secondary school students are educated in fields of education with the Maturita examination which consists of a state part and a part provided and guaranteed by the school.

Some subjects at secondary schools are taught by non-certified teachers. The greatest shortage of qualified teachers is reflected in IT/Informatics teaching (47.8% of IT/ Informatics teachers do not have the necessary qualifications).

Some public and private secondary schools in the Czech Republic specialize in IT and informatics study programmes.

AI curriculum has only recently been introduced into the new FEPs for secondary schools. And in relation to the issue of AI, one of the most successful graduates of a public Czech grammar school in 2023 is Matyáš Boháček who studies computer science at Stanford University in California.

Higher education (ISCED 4-7)

The Czech Higher education (public, private or state) institutions may be of a university or non-university type. Universities may offer all types of study programmes (i.e., bachelor's, master's and doctoral programmes) and carry out associated activities in science and research, development and innovation, as well as artistic or other creative activities. Non-university institutions offer mainly bachelor's study programmes; they can also offer master's programmes but not doctoral ones. Czech-language study programmes are free at public universities.

Primary or secondary school teachers must have university education; their studies take place at universities. Study programmes for Informatics/ Computer Science teachers are offered not only by faculties of education, but also by other faculties (e.g., Faculty of Mathematics and Physics at Charles University in Prague; Faculty of Science at Palacky University in Olomouc; Faculty of Informatics at Masaryk University in Brno).

1.3.2 Policy Documents

The Czech government has been developing a National AI Strategy to promote AI across various sectors, including education, in collaboration with AICZECHIA (see MPO, 2019; Czech Government, 2024). This strategy has led to funding for AI research and development, with universities encouraged to align their efforts with national priorities. The Strategy for Education Policy of the Czech Republic until 2030+ has guided the MŠMT in revising the curriculum and shaping government education strategies to ensure quality education at all levels. MŠMT's strategic objectives focus on improving competencies for active civic, professional, and personal life, while also addressing educational inequalities to support the development of all students. These goals are pursued through five key areas: i) Transforming the content, methods and assessment of education, ii) Equal access to quality education, iii) Support for teaching staff, iv) Increasing professional capacity, trust and mutual cooperation, and v) Increasing funding and ensuring its stability.

In 2022, Czech universities and educational initiatives, particularly the NPI ČR, began responding to the potential of GenAI in education. Recommendations were developed for school leaders, teachers, and parents on how to incorporate AI in education. The Czech School Inspectorate (ČŠI) oversees the quality of education and teachers' readiness for changes in the curriculum, including the integration of Informatics and the development of digital competencies. In 2024, ČŠI conducted a survey to assess schools' attitudes towards and readiness for GenAI integration in education (see ČŠI, 2024).

1.3.3 AI in Curriculum: AI Knowledge and GenAI Literacy

AI as a topic to be learnt

AI in curriculum for primary education (ISCED 1)

A theme about AI has not yet been introduced into the subject of Informatics in the new FEP for primary education. However, some primary school teachers teach about AI using materials focused on understanding the concept of AI that have been currently designed by a team of AIdetem.cz in co-operation with the NPI ČR. It is a set of nine teaching materials (lesson plans, presentations, worksheets) for pupils in the 3rd and 4th Year of primary education. The lessons about AI are based on the stories of two robots Ju and Pi, who want to help people so much, but often get everything wrong, guiding children through the concepts of data, machine learning, bias, large language models and ambient intelligence.

AI in curriculum for lower-secondary school education (ISCED 2)

In the curriculum of Informatics which has been newly included in the new FEP for lower-secondary schools, the theme on AI is not yet included. However, on the initiative of AIdětem, there is a set of teaching materials about AI dedicated to Informatics education at lower-secondary schools. One variant of how to introduce the curriculum about AI is based on the interactive story of two sprites William and Meriwether; pupils are taught to be able to give specific examples of data, to describe devices that are used to collect data, and understand the concept of machine learning. The starting point for the theoretical concept of AI and machine learning taught using AIdětem materials is the differences between algorithmic and machine learning approaches.

AI in curriculum for upper secondary school education (ISCED 3)

In the Informatics curriculum of the new Framework Education Programme for Secondary General Education (Grammar Schools) (FEP G), the topic of AI has already been introduced and is incorporated within the thematic unit Digital Technologies. Teaching is expected to address the following curriculum content: the principles of machine learning, AI applications, and the limits, benefits, and risks of AI.

AI study in Higher Education

- **AI courses and study programmes about AI:** Several universities (i.e., the Faculty of Mathematics and Physics at Charles University; the Faculty of IT at the Czech Technical University (CTU); the Faculty of Informatics at Masaryk University) offer dedicated study programmes in AI, machine learning, and data science.
- **Research in AI:** Czech institutions are active in AI and machine learning research, including work at CIIRC (CTU) and the Institute of Formal and Applied Linguistics (Charles University), which contribute to European-level initiatives in language technologies and large language models.

AI literacy within the broader development of digital competence

One of the key competences emphasised in the revised FEPs across ISCED 1–3 is digital competence. However, its definition does not explicitly require AI literacy competencies, and a formal national AI literacy framework is not embedded in compulsory schooling. GenAI use is not mandatory across subjects, yet many schools have begun

experimenting with AI on their own initiative (e.g., language teaching, arts education, and lesson planning support in STEM subjects). The NPI ČR portal (<https://rvp.cz/>) provides teachers with resources and guidance.

At the higher-education level, the response has been comparatively rapid. Under the leadership of PRG.AI and in cooperation with Charles University, the “AI ve vzdělávání” consortium was established as a platform for discussion, coordination, and exchange of experience across universities and, increasingly, with schools. Universities are also expanding training and guidance for staff and students in relation to academic integrity, responsible use, and the role of AI in thesis writing and research practice.

Overall, explicit curricular treatment of AI is currently strongest at ISCED 3 (FEP G), while ISCED 1–2 rely largely on supplementary materials, professional support structures, and school-level initiatives rather than formal curriculum requirements.

1.3.4 A System of Pre-service/ In-service Teacher Education

Since 1946, in the Czech Republic, teacher education has been carried out at universities according to approved accredited study programmes. The education for kindergarten teachers is carried out at the faculties of education in three-year bachelor's study programmes. The teacher education for primary education level (ISCED1) is carried out at the faculties of education in a five-year master's study.

In the Czech Republic there are nine faculties of education, the biggest one is the Faculty of Education at Charles University, in Prague. Universities that provide teacher education offer study programmes for full-time study (pre-service) or part-time studies (in-service teacher education).

Teacher education for ISCED2 or ISCED3 with specialisation in one or two school subjects is carried out in two-year accredited master's degree programmes at universities (not only at faculties of education). All these study programmes must meet the framework requirements issued by the MŠMT in 2024, upon completion of which the graduate obtains a professional qualification to practice the profession of teacher. A great emphasis in teacher education study programmes is placed on teaching practice.

All study programmes in the field of teacher education are aimed at fulfilling the Competence framework of a graduate teacher (hereafter referred to as the "Competence Framework"), approved by the MŠMT in 2023 (see MŠMT, 2023). The Competence Framework defines six areas of competence of a teaching graduate and their levels (graduate,

novice teacher, experienced teacher): (1) Taught subjects and their mediation to pupils; (2) Planning, management and reflection of teaching; (3) Learning environment; (4) Feedback and assessment; (5) Professional collaboration; and (6) Professional self-concept, development, ethics and mental health. Currently, it is not yet explicitly required that the issue of AI Literacy be part of university teacher education in the Czech Republic.

Integration of AI into In-service Teacher Education

Teachers need to be prepared both to use AI in their work and to teach about it. In the Czech Republic, this responsibility lies with nine faculties of education and several others involved in pre-service and in-service teacher education. At Charles University alone, five faculties are engaged in teacher education, with the Faculty of Education being the largest.

Each faculty operates autonomously, offering accredited study programmes that meet national quality standards. However, no study has yet examined how student or novice teachers in the Czech Republic are being introduced to AI during their university education.

At Charles University's Faculty of Education, researchers from the AI-EmpaTE project are active. Here, the course *Introduction to Artificial Intelligence in Education* is compulsory for MA students in IT and Informatics Education. Other student teachers, such as those in Maths, English or Music, may choose optional courses like *AI in Education* (offered by AIdetem.cz) or *Introduction to AI for Teachers*.

The faculty also organises workshops for student teachers and educators on using AI in teaching, including in foreign language education. Additionally, meetings of a national working group on generative AI in universities reveal that institutions across the Czech Republic are increasingly offering events and opportunities for students and teachers to explore AI's role in education.

To date, there is limited system-level evidence mapping how consistently AI-related competencies are embedded across teacher education providers, suggesting a need for coordinated monitoring and comparative evaluation.

1.3.5 Teacher Professional Development

In the Czech Republic, teachers are expected to engage in lifelong learning. Professional development is offered through universities, educational centres, and specialised providers. These opportunities often take the form of one-off courses, topical events, or sequenced training programmes, typically concluding with certification. Recent professional

development provision increasingly includes GenAI-related themes, reflecting demand for practical guidance as AI tools become more visible in school and academic contexts.

1.3.6 Initiatives and Support

State-led initiatives: implementation of policies focused on education

The NPI ČR responds to the arrival of generative AI tools such as ChatGPT and their spread among the general public by issuing recommendations. Thanks to their availability, it is possible to generate texts, images, videos and music. Such possibilities naturally transform teaching and bring with them new challenges. That is why NPI ČR comes with advice, help and support on how to deal with this new phenomenon in schools. In this way, they try to prevent inappropriate scenarios where schools ignore or ban unknown and unexpected AI tools. (see <https://digitalizace.rvp.cz/napric-predmety/ai#doporuceni>).

It turns out that for teachers who are trying to find help and support for finding and testing how to start using AI in teaching, in the work of a teacher, and for discussing the possible risks and problems associated with it, there are a number of events, websites, institutions, communities of experts in the Czech Republic:

Expert working group managed by NPI ČR

In the spring of 2023, an expert working group was therefore created in the NPI ČR, also on the basis of the impulse of the MŠMT which is in charge of the integration of AI in the framework of school support. It created a set of recommendations on how schools should approach AI. Recommendations are intended specifically for principals, teachers, pupils and parents.

ICT coordinators

ICT coordinators are (IT/Informatics) teachers who have completed a specialization study, which by the Czech law entitles them to work at schools, among other things, as consultants to teachers and advisors to school principals for the application of DT in education. The issue of AI has also been newly included in this study of ICT coordinators.

Courses for teachers

NPI ČR publishes an overview of AI-related professional development opportunities for teachers, including courses, workshops, and webinars, on its Digitalisation

portal: <https://digitalizace.rvp.cz/nabidka-podpory/kurzy-a-webinare#pro-ucitele>. For basic and secondary schools, the offer includes, for example, the webinar *AI and Machine Learning in Scratch*, delivered by Pavel Šiktanc.

Debates

NPI ČR organises a series of debates on AI (e.g., AI in education; AI and gifted pupils)

Events

NPI ČR supports the sharing of experience with the issue of digital technology, including AI, e.g. at DIGIevents "DIGI swimming pools" (DIGIevents are educational events intended for school principals and teachers who want to improve digital education, modernise education and move it into the era of the 21st century). Digiday #19: AI in practice; DigiDay #23: Communicating with AI - tips and tricks, etc.

Inspirations

NPI ČR seeks to support and inspire teachers in the use of AI. AI primary school teachers; AI in Math Education at Basic schools; AI in lesson plans for foreign languages teaching (basic schools, secondary schools); AI in Czech Language Education (basic school); AI in Math Education (secondary school); Introduction into AI (AI dětem and NPI ČR) (basic schools, secondary schools); Introduction into GenAI for teachers (basic school, secondary school), How to use Microsoft Copilot and AI in education (basic schools, secondary schools).

NPI ČR supports the sharing of experience with teaching new informatics, with the issue of digital technology, including AI, e.g. at DIGIevents "DIGI swimming pools" (DIGIevents are educational events intended for school principals and teachers who want to improve digital education, modernise education and move it into the era of the 21st century).

Articles, resources, newsletters

NPI ČR supports publishing articles and teaching materials on AI on the Methodological Portal RVP.CZ (e.g., *Pedagogika nejistoty v éře AI* by Brdička (2024)).

Recordings of programmes on the issue of AI in education are published on <https://digitalizace.rvp.cz/napric-predmety/ai>

Recommendations, legal aspects

NPI ČR publishes recommendations for schools on the use of artificial intelligence in primary and secondary education in the resource Doporučení školám pro využívání umělé inteligence na základních a středních školách, available here: <https://digitalizace.rvp.cz/napric-predmety/ai#webinar-a-kurzy>.

The same NPI ČR Digitalisation portal also provides guidance addressing whether the use of AI in schools is legal, with further information available at:

<https://digitalizace.rvp.cz/napric-predmety/ai> and <https://digitalizace.rvp.cz/g>.

Principles how to use GenAI

The National Pedagogical Institute of the Czech Republic (NPI ČR) has developed guidance leaflets for schools entitled “Zásady pro využívání generativní umělé inteligence” [Principles for the Use of Generative Artificial Intelligence]. These materials outline key recommendations for the responsible and appropriate use of GenAI in school contexts and are available at <https://www.npi.cz/aktuality/74837-doporuceni-jak-pracovat-s-umelou-inteligenci>.

Study materials

NPI ČR supports the creation of learning materials for pupils and teachers (e.g., a set of materials "AI Curriculum: A Comprehensive Guide to Teaching AI at Primary and Secondary Schools" developed by the team AIdětem.cz).

Teachers' digital competencies development

As part of the national project NPO 3.1 - AIDIG focused on the development of teachers' digital competences according to the European Competence Framework DigCompEdu, the Czech Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports supports and will support in Activity 2 the development of teachers' digital competencies also for AI in teaching, disinformation, cybersecurity. The implementer of AIDIG is NPI ČR. Umělá inteligence do škol (<https://aidoskol.cz/umela-inteligence-do-skol/>)

Regional support to schools

The Czech Republic is administratively divided into 14 regions, and each region is supported by regional coordinators based in the regional offices of the National Pedagogical Institute of the Czech Republic (NPI ČR). These coordinators provide localised guidance for schools and facilitate access to consultation and support services (e.g., KIM and ITguru) to help educators and school leaders implement digitalisation initiatives, including emerging areas such as AI in education. The regional support structure is outlined here: <https://digitalizace.rvp.cz/nabidka-podpory/podpora-v-regionu>.

Grassroots initiatives

Since the beginning, when GenAI tools appeared, which could already be used in education, various initiatives to support AI in education have begun to emerge in the Czech Republic. Here are the most significant initiatives:

- **Consortium Artificial Intelligence Charles University:** A Platform about AI in education for Czech schools including universities (initiative of representants of the Czech universities and HEI) managed by prg.ai and the Rectorate of Charles University.
- **Aidětem** (aidetem.cz), non-profit initiative AI for children, which is a leader in education in the field of AI in the Czech Republic.
- **PRG.AI** (<https://prg.ai/>, <https://prg.ai/en/about-us/>)
- **AIAcademy** (<https://www.mlcollege.com/ai-academy/>) offers open courses (<https://www.mlcollege.com/#courses>), summer schools, and practical learning programmes in machine learning for beginners and intermediate learners; only basic high-school mathematics and Python are expected. It also provides open-access learning materials for the general public on key AI topics (e.g., AI basics and history, data and interpretation, risks, and ethical issues): <https://www.mlcollege.com/umela-intelligence-pro-kazdeho/>.
- **Aignos** (<https://www.aignos.cz/>) offers original educational workshops, lectures and seminars on AI for children (workshops Human in the AI era; FaiKE - When AI lies and misinforms; We create with AI, etc.) or for teachers (AI courses for teachers; AI in school rules - how to set rules?, etc.), for schools or companies.
- **One World in Schools** (jsns.cz) - one of the educational programmes of the People in Need organisation.

1.3.7 Local Challenges, Opportunities, and Barriers

AI is increasingly entering Czech schools, supported by initiatives that help educators explore its educational potential. The ongoing curricular reform across all school levels creates favourable conditions by integrating digital competence and introducing a new subject in Informatics.

Another key strength is the growing collaboration among academics and young experts in computing, robotics, AI and social sciences. They are working together to support schools in understanding and using AI creatively and critically. This presents a valuable opportunity for meaningful integration of AI in education.

In the Czech Republic, basic art schools (ZUŠ) have a long tradition. These schools are managed by the MŠMT. ZUŠ may offer elementary, secondary, post-secondary, or undergraduate programmes. They are educational institutions with a primary focus on visual arts (especially illustration, painting, photography, sculpture, design and graphic design), music (playing on musical instruments such as piano, violin, flauta, etc. or singing), dancing or theatre. The ZUŠ are attended by primary and secondary school pupils as well as adults as extracurricular activities - out of their own interest in their free time, sometimes also to prepare for studying at one of the arts secondary schools or universities. In 2023/24, there were 513 ZUŠ with more than 262,149 students (ČŠI, 2024). Some ZUŠs teach both visual and performing arts, while others are specialised in only one of the two areas. Similar to all other Czech schools, the ZUŠ focuses on the development of the key competences of their students. One of them is the digital competence defined by the Strategy 2030+ document in MŠMT (2020). In this area, a number of ZUŠ are currently working on the issues of using AI. In order for ZUŠ teachers to be trained for using AI, ZUŠs use the offers of various educational companies - one of them is Aignos.cz.

1.3.8 Conclusion

According to the findings of the NPI (Matoušek, 2025), for the time being only about 20% of Czech teachers use AI in their pedagogical work, primarily to prepare their teaching lessons or as their "courtesy" digital assistant. AI is also used by some school principals who consult with AI about some of their plans or use it to make work more efficient. While in grammar schools (ISCED 3) AI is already an essentially "automated tool" for more than 75% of school managers, in basic schools (ISCED 1-2) only less than 48% of survey participants

use AI. In secondary schools, 68% of principals and their representatives work with it, 2/3 of them even work with AI in their spare time.

Overall, the Czech Republic combines a strong structural reform agenda (FEP revision, compulsory informatics, and cross-curricular digital competence) with an increasingly robust support ecosystem (NPI ČR guidance, regional coordinators, professional development, and civil-society initiatives). However, the limited explicit integration of AI literacy into ISCED 1–2 curricula and the uneven distribution of teacher expertise suggest that scaling responsible AI integration will require targeted capacity-building, clearer competency expectations, and systematic monitoring across educational levels.

1.4 SLOVAK REPUBLIC

Education in Slovakia is free at all levels. According to available data, around 93.7% of kindergartens, 90% of primary schools, and 78% of secondary schools are state-run. Compulsory education lasts from age 5 to 16, beginning with one mandatory year in kindergarten and continuing through the 9th grade of primary school.

In 2023, the Minister of Education approved a new State Education Programme (SEP) as part of the curriculum reform under the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (Bútora, 2023). The reform aims to modernise education for the 21st century. From September 2023, 40 primary schools began implementing the new curriculum, which all schools must adopt from the 2026/2027 academic year, starting with Year 1. The new approach focuses on applying knowledge in practice rather than rote memorisation. Computer science education is also being updated to better reflect the role of digital technologies in modern life.

Student testing results in international comparisons have been poor for a long time. Slovakia participates in several comparisons:

- **PISA 2022:** In the OECD PISA 2022 study, a representative sample of 15-year-olds in Slovakia was assessed in mathematics, reading, and science literacy, with mathematics as the main focus. While Slovak pupils had matched the OECD average in mathematics in PISA 2018, their 2022 scores fell below the average. Similar underperformance was observed in reading and science, consistent with previous cycles..
- **OECD PIAAC 2023:** In 2022-2023, the second cycle of the international PIAAC 2023 research was carried out in Slovakia, in which 31 countries participated. The level of reading literacy, mathematical literacy and adaptive problem solving was monitored on a representative sample of 16- to 65-year-old adults. Slovakia ranked below the OECD

average in reading literacy and in adaptive problem solving, and was at the OECD average in mathematical literacy. A positive finding is that adults with secondary education in Slovakia had significantly higher scores than those with secondary education in the OECD average in all three literacy skills. The same applies to adults with primary education.

- **TIMSS 2023:** In the school year 2022/2023, the eighth cycle of the international TIMSS study, which is conducted under the auspices of the IEA, took place in Slovakia. In Slovakia, 162 primary schools and 4 788 fourth-graders took part in the testing. Slovak pupils performed better than the average of the countries involved in the study, but in mathematics the result is significantly lower than the average of both OECD and EU countries. In science, Slovak pupils' performance is on a par with the average of OECD and EU countries (Galádová, 2024).
- **ICILS 2023:** Slovakia participated for the second time in the ICILS (International Computer and Information Literacy Study), which assesses students' readiness for life and work in the digital age. In 2023, 166 schools and 3,034 students took part. While Slovak students scored above the ICILS 2023 international average, their performance declined notably compared to ICILS 2013. As in the previous cycle, student performance was strongly linked to socio-economic background (Panáčková & Barčiaková, 2024).
- **PIRLS 2021:** In Slovakia, 169 primary schools, 4,841 pupils, 275 teachers of these pupils, 165 school principals and approximately 4,270 parents of the tested pupils participated in the testing. Slovak pupils achieved a better result than the average of the PIRLS scale and comparable to the average of both EU and OECD countries.

Recent international assessments show mixed results for Slovakia's students. In PISA 2022, 15-year-olds scored below the OECD average in mathematics, reading, and science. PIAAC 2023 results were similar, except adults with secondary education outperformed the OECD average. In TIMSS 2023, fourth-graders scored above the global average, though below OECD and EU levels in mathematics. ICILS 2023 results were above the global average but declined from the previous cycle. In PIRLS 2021, reading scores aligned with OECD and EU averages.

1.4.1 Structure of Educational System

The education system in Slovakia is designed to provide comprehensive support to learners at all stages, aligned with the International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED). It encompasses pre-primary, primary, lower secondary, upper secondary, and higher

education, with a strong emphasis on digital competences and informatics education. Schools and educational facilities are described. We can see the web page Ministry of education.

Pre-primary education (ISCED 0)

Pre-primary education (ISCED020) in Slovakia is focused on supporting the holistic development of children aged 3 to 6 years (some children may attend preschool until 7 years old). The emphasis is on developing basic skills and abilities necessary for further education in primary schools. Kindergarten are educational institutions providing pre-primary education.

Basic or primary education (ISCED 1) and lower secondary education (ISCED2)

Basic (elementary) schools in Slovakia provide compulsory education, which lasts 9 years. The education is divided into two stages: the first stage is oriented on basic education - 4 years (ISCED 1) and the second stage represents- 5 years (ISCED 2), with education designed to support the comprehensive development of pupils. The basic school is intended for children from 6 to 15 years of age. The Slovak education system allows the postponement of entering the 1st year of primary school. The new curriculum divides 9 years (primary and lower secondary) of education into three cycles.

Mandatory subject computer science (informatics) was introduced at the primary level (first cycle) of Slovak schools starting in the 2023/2024 academic year as part of a curricular reform. This reform reflects the need to develop digital skills in pupils to prepare them for a technology-driven society. At the basic level, computer science focuses on basic digital literacy, the safe use of technology, and foundational principles of algorithmic thinking. Through playful and engaging methods, children are introduced to the basics of working with computers, tablets, and other digital tools.

Upper secondary education (ISCED3)

In Slovakia, secondary education (ISCED 3) is offered by general upper secondary schools (gymnasiums), specialised vocational schools, and conservatoires. Admission requires completion of compulsory schooling or basic education, along with passing entrance requirements. Informatics education varies by school type and curriculum. Gymnasiums must offer at least one hour of informatics per week for two years, though vocational schools may provide more extensive IT training. However, the current allocation of informatics hours often falls short of the demands of modern digital literacy.

As of the 2024/2025 academic year, around 10% of teachers in Slovakia lack the required qualifications, reflecting broader challenges such as teacher shortages and limited professional development. A 2022 IT Academy survey revealed that 20% of schools have no qualified informatics teacher. The shortage of qualified teachers in this field remains a persistent issue. In 2022, only 1.2% of education students were preparing to become informatics teachers—far below national needs. Estimates from local authorities and the ministry indicate a shortage of 2,000–3,000 teachers, especially in physics, computer science, ethics, and technology.

1.4.2 Policy Documents

Teaching AI in primary schools in Slovakia is not yet systematically included in the official curriculum. However, in recent years, there have been efforts to integrate basic concepts of AI and related topics into the teaching of informatics and digital technologies.

Current Situation

- **Curricular Reform:** As part of the curricular reform introduced in the 2023/2024 school year, informatics became a mandatory subject starting from the first stage of primary school. While AI-related topics are not yet mandatory, they can be part of the broader educational framework focusing on digital skills.
- **Teaching AI in subject Informatics:** Some schools are beginning to experiment with teaching basic uses of AI and machine learning. These topics are still in the early stages of implementation. AI basics may be taught through activities involving robotics, programming, and algorithms. Schools might introduce AI through visual tools and games that encourage children to learn the fundamentals of these technologies.
- **Pilot Projects and Initiatives:** Some schools and educational platforms are introducing pilot projects focused on AI for children. Examples include using simple programming tools like Scratch or Blockly, which teach logical thinking and basic algorithmic principles that form the foundation of understanding AI.
- **Educational Initiatives:** Various educational initiatives, such as courses, workshops, and online materials, are emerging that focus on AI and are available to primary school students. These initiatives are still developing and are not yet part of the regular curriculum.

Teachers who want to use/teach AI in regional education often look for information in other countries, e.g. the Czech Republic AI for children. As part of the national DITED project (from 2024), webinars, training for teachers focused on AI in regional education are underway.

Teaching AI to future teachers in Slovakia is a critical step in equipping educators with the skills and knowledge needed to integrate modern technologies into the classroom. Several initiatives and programmes are in place to prepare pedagogy students to work effectively with AI.

Specialised Training and Certifications

The National Institute for Education and Youth (NIVaM) organises training sessions and workshops for both future and current teachers, covering topics such as: using AI for lesson planning, effectively leveraging digital assistants and tools to create interactive activities, preparing for challenges associated with the digital transformation of education.

Projects and Initiatives

- **IT Academy – Education for the 21st Century:** Provides innovative learning materials focused on AI, accessible to student teachers.
- **Digital Transformation of Education (DiTEdu):** Prepares digital coordinators and trainers to disseminate AI knowledge among educators.

1.4.3 AI in Curriculum: AI Knowledge and GenAI Literacy

AI Knowledge is part of a reform that is oriented on modernizing and adapting the knowledge and teaching of digital technologies to better prepare students for the challenges of the 21st century. The reform is based on the need to improve pupils' digital skills and prepare them for a world that is increasingly dependent on technology. Key changes in computer science under curriculum reform:

- **Strengthening the teaching of informatics at all educational levels**

Informatics has become a mandatory subject starting from primary schools. The reform focuses on developing digital skills, as well as understanding the basics of programming, algorithms, computer security, and data management. In secondary schools, more advanced topics are introduced, including programming, AI, and technologies like Internet of Things (IoT) and digital security.

- **Focus on critical thinking and problem-solving**

The reform promotes teaching that encourages students to think analytically and solve problems independently using technology.

- **Digital literacy and security**

A significant aspect of the reform is teaching cybersecurity, which is becoming a part of the curriculum.

- **Introduction of new methods and materials**

Informatics teachers are being trained in new methodologies to teach more effectively and apply modern technologies in their teaching.

- **Access to technology**

The reform aims to ensure that schools have access to the necessary hardware and software to support informatics teaching, which is essential for quality teaching in programming, robotics, and other modern technologies.

- **Focus on interactivity and practical skills**

The goal of the reform is for students to not only be passive consumers of technology but also active creators. This means emphasising practical skills such as programming, creating websites, applications, and even the basics of AI.

1.4.4 A System of Pre-service/ In-service Teacher Education

All these study programmes must be accredited by the Slovak Accreditation Agency for Higher Education. It is the public institution whose task is to perform external quality assurance activities in higher education in the Slovak Republic. It was established in 2018. The mission of the Agency is to contribute to improving the quality of higher education through modern tools following the European Standards for Quality Assurance in Higher Education. The Agency is intended to provide a mirror of quality to higher education institutions and to decide on the granting of appropriate accreditations following the law. The Agency is an advisory brand of the Government of the Slovak Republic in assessing applications of higher education institutions, and also takes over the decision-making authority of the Minister of Education, Science, Research and Sports of the Slovak Republic. New standards for Study Programmes are effective from 1 September 2024.

In the Slovak Republic, teacher education has been carried out at universities according to approved accredited study programmes. The education for kindergarten teachers is carried out at the faculties of education in three-year bachelor's study programmes. The teacher

education for primary education level (ISCED1) is carried out at the faculties of education in a five-year master's study. There are five faculties of education in Slovakia.

Teacher education for lower secondary education (ISCED2) or upper secondary education (ISCED3) with specialisation in one or two school subjects (so called combinations) is carried out in two-year accredited master's degree programmes at universities (by faculties of education, natural sciences, philosophical and others). There are specified requirements issued by the Ministry of Education, Culture and Sports, upon completion of which the graduate obtains a professional qualification to practice the profession of teacher. Applicants can be admitted to these two-year master's programmes (in the range of 120 credits) who have already completed a related bachelor's degree programme in the range of 180 credits (while the scope of preparation in a specific field must be in the minimum range of 50 credits). Great emphasis in teacher training study programmes is placed on teaching practice. Universities that provide teacher education offer study programmes for full-time study (pre-service), or part-time studies (in-service teacher education).

1.4.5 Teacher Professional Development

In Slovakia, 10 universities prepare future teachers. However, some universities only train first-level teachers in primary schools, and others only train specialist teachers in computer science, mathematics, and physics (for example). Each university dealing with (pre- and in-service) teacher education is essentially autonomous, educating future teachers on the basis of accredited study programmes that must meet certain required quality parameters.

Several Slovak universities have incorporated AI into Master's-level teacher education programmes. Comenius University (Faculty of Mathematics, Physics and Informatics, Bratislava) offers *Introduction to Artificial Intelligence* for future informatics teachers, covering AI in the curriculum, decision trees, machine learning, neural networks, AI in gaming, data pattern recognition, and the Turing test. Pavol Jozef Šafárik University (Faculty of Natural Sciences, Košice) also offers a similarly titled course, which includes AI tools, machine learning, neural networks, robotics, AI in art and entertainment, chatbots, ethical and legal aspects, and design thinking exercises.

At the University of Constantine the Philosopher (Faculty of Natural Sciences and Informatics, Nitra), two AI-oriented courses are offered: one on foundational AI concepts, and another focused on informatics didactics, incorporating AI-based teaching projects. Matej Bel University (Faculty of Natural Sciences, Banská Bystrica) provides three elective courses

which are *Artificial Intelligence*, *Neural Networks*, and *Genetic Algorithms*, as well as a compulsory course on informatics teaching methodology with a focus on AI. This course includes the use of machine learning and GenAI in lesson planning and problem-solving, emphasising the analysis of GenAI-generated solutions.

In this context, Škrinárová et al. (2024) conducted a qualitative analysis of graph problem-solving with ChatGPT, presented at Didinfo 2024 (Liberec, Czech Republic), and Knežník, Škrinárová, and Voštinár developed an AI-focused teaching methodology, presented at Didinfo 2021 in Banská Bystrica.

Matej Bel University in Banská Bystrica arranged an educational event on February 6, 2025, titled "*AI in Education*". This event is aimed at UMB staff, including educators and doctoral students, focusing on understanding the principles of AI and its application in teaching. (umb.sk)

University teachers are recently or currently working on national projects KEGA (Cultural and Educational Grant Agency) focused on teaching AI:

- KEGA 018UMB-4/2020 Implementation of new trends in computer science to teaching algorithmic thinking and programming in Informatics for secondary education (2020 - 2022).
- KEGA 016STU-4/2021 New forms of education for crisis management (e.g., COVID-19) using AI (2021-2023).
- KEGA 008ŽU-4/2021 Integrated Teaching of AI Methods at the University of Žilina (2021-2023).
- KEGA 010UPJŠ-4/2024 Use of AI in Teaching School Informatics in Secondary Schools (2024-2026).
- KEGA 032EU-4/2024 Creating an educational model to enhance the skills of non-programming university students in the use of artificial intelligence tools for business and entrepreneurship support (2024-2026).
- KEGA 006SPU-4/2024 Opportunities and limitations of the educational support role of AI systems based on large language models (LLM) for teachers and students in the Landscape Engineering degree programme.

1.4.6 Initiatives and Support

In Slovakia, several initiatives and organisations support the incorporation of AI in schools:

- **Programme for Digital Competencies for Teachers:** This programme, organised by JA Slovakia, offers accredited innovation training for primary and secondary school teachers. It focuses on developing digital skills and integrating modern tools, including AI, into teaching.
- **Association for Ethics and Development in AI:** This association connects companies, educational institutions, and individuals to promote AI education and development. One of its goals is to train teachers in AI to use it effectively in classrooms.
- **AI for kids Initiative (AI dětem):** This initiative focuses on educating teachers in the Czech Republic and Slovakia about AI. In the first half of 2024, they trained ten thousand teachers to simplify administrative tasks and enrich the teaching process using AI tools.
- **AI Slovakia AI:** The initiative civic association bringing together Slovak partners in the field of AI.

These initiatives aim to modernise the Slovak education system and prepare students for a digital future by integrating AI into educational practices.

Events

Several educational activities for teachers (not only computer science) are organised in Slovakia.

- International conference DidInfo, whose aims are to discuss current trends in the field of computer science didactics to share experiences with the teaching of informatics even in a non-traditional (hybrid/distance) form at all types of schools, one of the goals is also research in the field of AI in education. <https://www.didinfo.net/sk/>
- Conference, workshops, webinars, national project DITED. The goal of the national project is to create a sustainable system of support for the digital transformation of education based on research directly at schools and relevant data. <https://nivam.sk/np-ditedu/>
- Informatics Day - an event intended for primary and secondary school teachers. The event annually helps to disseminate the results of the work of ODI employees and our students and graduates among the teaching community, mainly in the field of teaching informatics, but also in the field of AI in teaching. <https://informatickyden.sk/>

Courses

In addition to several foreign courses focused on AI, Slovak teachers can use or participate in several courses. Most of the courses are paid, some can be used by teachers as part of refresher training, some are intended for a wide audience.

- Introduction to AI for users (Úvod do umelej inteligencie pre užívateľov)
- Introduction to AI in practice (Úvod do umelej inteligencie v praxi)
- Elements of AI (<https://course.elementsofai.com/sk/>)
- AI course practically I. (Kurz umelá inteligencia prakticky I),
- AI in Education: Resources and Study Opportunities (Umelá inteligencia v oblasti vzdelávania: Zdroje a študijné príležitosti) <https://learn.microsoft.com/sk-sk/training/educator-center/topics/ai-for-education>

Social Media

Many teachers in Slovakia use various social networks to obtain information and communicate with other teachers. The teachers used for communicate with various Facebook groups. The most used groups for not only computer science teachers are:

- We teach computer science (Učíme informatiku), social network with more than 10 000 members <https://www.facebook.com/groups/UcimeInformatiku>
- Computer Science teachers, ideas, links, advice (Učitelia Informatiky, nápady, odkazy, rady), approximately 3 800 members, <https://www.facebook.com/groups/uciteliainformatiky>
- School Digital Coordinator (Školský digitálny koordinátor), approximately 1 700 members, <https://www.facebook.com/groups/skolskydigitalnykoordinator>
- We teach with technology (Učíme s technológiami), more than 1 900 members, <https://www.facebook.com/groups/ucimestechnologiami>
- We teach computer science differently (Učíme informatiku inak), more than 3 600 members, <https://www.facebook.com/groups/ucme.informatiku.inak>

Recommendations for schools, universities

Universities and schools in Slovakia are currently creating guidelines and recommendations for the use of AI in education (Takáč, 2024), (Cotton et.al., 2024).

Recommendations for university teachers from an educational point of view: AI tools should be used in such a way that they support the basic goal of higher education - the

development of knowledge and skills. Since these tools are increasingly part of work processes and their knowledge is required by employers, it is advisable for students to learn to use them in an ethical way and to recognize their limits and risks.

Recommendations in context of using the AI tools are most often mentioned in connection with writing essays or theses. Using AI tools to directly develop whole texts, formulating conclusions and any claims that are supposed to be the result of independent work can be an academic fraud. However, AI tools can (as long as it is in accordance with the rules set by the teacher) help e.g. in providing tips, designing the structure of research and experiments, automatic translation of texts, summarising articles, stylistic adjustments and correcting grammatical errors. Any use of AI tools in text processing (apart from purely formal editing) must be acknowledged and properly cited.

Recommendations contain positive examples of using AI for students and teachers, positive examples of using AI in classes, safety when working with AI tools.

Other projects and initiatives

In recent years, many projects and initiatives have been created that focus on various forms and ways of incorporating AI into education:

- The schools that changes word (Školy ktoré menia svet).
 - AI in education and what we need about it – first part, <https://skolyktoremeniasvet.sk/umela-inteligencia-vo-vzdelavani-co-o-nej-potrebuje-vediet-1-cast/>
 - AI in education tips and tricks- second part, <https://skolyktoremeniasvet.sk/umela-inteligencia-vo-vzdelavani-tipy-a-triky-2-cast/>
- AI in school. Listen to Kecalek: 69 GPT prompts for teachers (POČÚVAŤ KECÁLKA: 69 GPT PROMPTOV PRE UČITEĽOV. <https://www.aivskole.sk/>)

1.4.7 Local Challenges, Opportunities, and Barriers

Example: AI as an assistant for students at basic school to create own song

At the primary school Ďumbierska 17 in Banská Bystrica there is a teacher of informatics who tries to use new technologies in teaching informatics at the second level. In November 2024, she gave the pupils the task of creating arbitrary text and music using AI. They could use any GenAI. Most of the pupils (14-16 years old) used ChatGPT to generate the

text. They could have used different websites to create a song, but most of them were paid (or did not allow downloading the created songs to the computer). Therefore, towards the end of the lesson, she advised them to use <https://ilovesong.ai/>. All pupils completed the task, they were able to create the lyrics of the song and then compose the music for it. The teacher's primary goal was to encourage independent problem-solving.

1.4.8 Conclusion

In Slovakia, various coordinated and independent initiatives are promoting the integration of GenAI in education across all ISCED levels. The Ministry of Education supports the ethical and age-appropriate use of AI, notably through national projects such as *IT Academy: Education for the 21st Century* and *Digital Transformation of Education*. The National Institute for Education and Youth also plays an active role.

GenAI is most extensively implemented in universities with computer science and AI-focused programmes, particularly those preparing future computer science teachers. These graduates are well-equipped to use GenAI in their teaching, understand its benefits and risks, and often serve as ambassadors for GenAI adoption across subjects. Matej Bel University in Banská Bystrica, organiser of the 30th *DidInfo* international conference, plays a key role in promoting AI use among primary and secondary school teachers.

Many teachers independently create resources such as courses, websites, and online communities to support their peers in adopting GenAI. These tools aid in lesson planning, instruction, and assessment. To use GenAI effectively and responsibly, modern teachers must be ethically grounded and capable of guiding students accordingly. Students, too, must be prepared to use GenAI critically, as misuse can result in misinformation or harmful outcomes. Ethical and informed AI use is essential both in education and society at large.

Chapter Conclusions

This chapter examined the current state of AI in education in Latvia, Israel, the Czech Republic, and Slovakia through the lens of policy implementation frameworks (Matland, 1995; Mthethwa, 2012). It addressed four guiding questions: the dominant approach to implementation, the mechanisms that embed AI policy across educational levels, the critical areas requiring further strengthening, and the national level actions most needed to advance AI in education responsibly and effectively.

Across all four contexts, AI is advancing through a hybrid implementation pattern that combines top down measures, such as national strategies, regulations, guidelines, and system level programmes, with bottom up activity led by schools, universities, professional communities, and non governmental or private actors. This combination appears to be enabling both coordination and experimentation, while also creating variation in pace and quality of implementation across educational levels and regions. A key implication is that implementation should continue to support both pathways, while improving their alignment so that local innovation informs national direction and national guidance supports local capacity.

Communication between stakeholders exists in every country, but it is not consistently structured or embedded as a routine feedback loop within the education ecosystem. Weak or episodic feedback risks reducing coherence between policy intent and classroom or institutional practice. Strengthening implementation therefore requires mapping core stakeholders and institutionalising communication channels that connect policymakers, school leaders, teachers, teacher educators, parents, and school IT staff. Such channels can support iterative refinement, faster identification of risks, and a more realistic translation of policy into practice.

In all four countries, digitalisation policies and infrastructures provide an important foundation for AI integration. Although digitalisation is not equivalent to AI readiness, existing governance structures, competence frameworks, professional development systems, and investment instruments can be leveraged to reduce fragmentation and accelerate implementation. The practical challenge is to move from general digital competence ambitions to explicit AI literacy expectations that are developmentally appropriate across educational stages and that are accompanied by usable pedagogical guidance.

The chapter also highlights a persistent gap between competency aspirations and classroom enactment. While competency language is emerging, detailed pedagogical supports, validated examples, and clear guidance for assessment are still unevenly available. The next phase of implementation should therefore prioritise the development or refinement of national maps of AI-related competencies, paired with accessible repositories of guidelines, teaching approaches, and evidence informed best practices that help educators operationalise these competencies across subjects and levels.

Several critical areas require systematic attention to ensure responsible and sustainable AI integration. Ethics and academic integrity require clear expectations for disclosure, acceptable use, authorship, plagiarism, and intellectual property. Privacy and data protection

require AI specific safeguards, transparent rules for AI-enabled systems, and capacity building for schools and universities to apply these safeguards confidently. Equity and accessibility remain central, given the risk that AI opportunities concentrate in better resourced schools and regions. Finally, teacher capacity remains a decisive factor, as uneven preparedness and limited time for professional learning can slow implementation even when policy is supportive.

National level progress depends on widening the focus beyond teachers and students to the broader ecosystem that shapes implementation. Priorities therefore include structured and scalable training aligned with competency expectations, differentiated support for stakeholder groups such as parents, teacher educators, and IT specialists, and the institutionalisation of cross stakeholder collaboration. Establishing national databases of tools, activities, guidelines, and vetted practices can further support coherence, reduce duplication, and strengthen trust.

Overall, the four countries show strong momentum for AI integration, supported by policy activity, emerging competence agendas, and growing practitioner engagement. The next stage of development will depend on stronger coordination between top down direction and bottom up practice, clearer pedagogical translation of AI literacy aims, and ecosystem wide capacity building to ensure that AI integration is ethical, equitable, and educationally meaningful (Matland, 1995; Mthethwa, 2012).

CHAPTER 2

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE-LITERACY FRAMEWORK

This chapter presents an AI literacy framework aimed at supporting pre-service and in-service teachers in effectively integrating GenAI tools into their teaching practice, specifically in the preparation, delivery, and evaluation of educational materials. The framework is grounded in data collected through an online questionnaire developed by the project partners and distributed to pre-service and in-service teachers across four countries, as well as insights from focus group interviews with teacher educators and parents. It draws on the six-component model proposed by Tenberga and Daniela (2024), encompassing understanding, critical evaluation, ethics, usage, awareness, and communication. The results not only inform the proposed framework but also contribute to the development of a practical tool to guide teachers in applying GenAI in educational settings, in line with the objectives of the AI-EmpaTe project.

2.1 METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a mixed-methods research design (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018) to support the development of an AI literacy framework for pre-service and in-service teachers who are integrating generative AI (GenAI) tools into educational practice. The framework is grounded in empirical evidence drawn from (a) an online questionnaire and (b) focus group interviews, together providing a comprehensive picture of teachers' experiences, needs, and perceptions related to GenAI.

Survey design and participants

An online survey was distributed between December 2024 and February 2025 to pre-service and in-service teachers in Latvia, Israel, the Czech Republic, and Slovakia through professional networks and social media channels. In total, 1,035 respondents participated (473 pre-service teachers and 562 in-service teachers).

The questionnaire included two sections. The first collected demographic and professional information (e.g., gender, age, educational background, teaching experience, subject area, and current use of GenAI tools). The second comprised 25 closed-ended items measured on a five-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree) assessing

familiarity with GenAI, classroom-related use, and attitudes and perceptions. Three open-ended questions were also included to elicit more detailed reflections.

The survey instrument was informed by a targeted review of research on GenAI in education and drew conceptually on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davis, 1989). Items were organised around five thematic areas: (1) lesson planning with GenAI, (2) teaching with GenAI, (3) assessment using GenAI, (4) ethical and responsible use of GenAI, and (5) professional development in GenAI.

Focus groups: design, participants, and analysis

To complement survey findings and deepen contextual understanding, focus group (FG) interviews were conducted in each country with two stakeholder groups: teacher educators and parents. The study design aimed for one FG per stakeholder group in each country (eight focus groups in total), with approximately five participants per group.

In practice, 23 parents participated overall (Israel: 10; Latvia: 5; Slovakia: 5; Czech Republic: 3). Focus groups with teacher educators involved 21 participants in total (Israel: 5; Latvia: 5; Slovakia: 5; Czech Republic: 6). Participants were recruited by the national research teams and represented a range of professional backgrounds and levels of digital literacy.

All focus groups were audio-recorded with informed consent. Each national team transcribed and analysed the data using thematic analysis guided by a shared set of project-developed questions and predefined thematic areas. Teams coded their transcripts locally (e.g., segmenting responses into matrices aligned with guiding questions and then inductively clustering themes), and subsequently produced country protocols. These country-level outputs were synthesised to enable comparative analysis across the four national contexts.

Integration of findings for framework development

Together, the quantitative survey results and qualitative focus group insights provided an evidence base for the AI literacy framework, highlighting priority competencies, recurring challenges, and the support structures required to promote ethical, context-sensitive, and pedagogically meaningful use of GenAI in education.

2.1.1 Existing AI-Literacy Frameworks

As AI technologies become increasingly embedded in educational contexts, the need for comprehensive AI literacy frameworks has grown significantly. These frameworks aim to

equip learners and educators with the competencies required to understand, use, evaluate, and engage ethically with AI. Most models share a progression from basic awareness to more advanced application and critical reflection (Ng et al., 2021; Wang & Lester, 2023).

One of the most referenced models is the AI Literacy Framework by Ng et al. (2021), which includes three core levels: awareness, understanding, and application. This structure supports foundational AI knowledge and encourages the responsible use of AI tools. Extending this, Yue et al. (2025) introduce a pedagogical framework called *Students as AI Literate Designers (SAILD)*, rooted in design-based learning. Their model emphasises four dimensions of AI literacy: knowledge, skills, ethics, and attitudes, and is specifically tailored for elementary education.

The AI4K12 Initiative (Touretzky et al., 2022) presents the widely adopted Five Big Ideas which are Perception, Representation & Reasoning, Learning, Natural Interaction, and Social Impact, framing AI literacy as an interdisciplinary and developmentally appropriate concept across K–12. Meanwhile, Digital Promise (2024) offers a practice-oriented framework emphasising understanding, evaluating, and using AI, encouraging ethical engagement in real-world contexts.

In the policy space, frameworks for the classification of AI-related competencies have emerged. The OECD AI Competency Framework (2022) outlines understanding and interaction with AI as priorities in both workplace and educational contexts. Meanwhile, UNESCO's AI Competencies Framework (2024) promotes a balanced development of technical fluency and responsible, human-centred AI practices.

A recent and significant addition is the Supplement to the DigCompEDU Framework (Bekiaridis & Attwell, 2024), which details AI-related skills and competences for educators. Positioned within the broader DigCompEDU digital competence model, this supplement emphasises educators' roles not only as AI users but also as facilitators of AI understanding among students. It highlights competences in areas such as AI-supported personalisation, bias awareness, and ethical integration, offering a holistic roadmap for educators working with AI-enhanced learning environments.

Altogether, these frameworks reflect a shift from purely technical understanding toward critical, ethical, and pedagogical engagement with AI. They advocate for AI literacy as a core competence for both students and educators, supporting thoughtful integration across curriculum and instruction in line with global educational goals.

2.1.2 AI Literacy Framework Used for this Project

The AI literacy framework developed by Tenberga and Daniela (2024) was chosen specifically for its comprehensive nature and strong relevance to educational contexts, particularly teacher preparation and classroom practice. Compared to other frameworks reviewed such as the AI Literacy Framework by Ng et al. (2021), the AI4K12 Initiative (Touretzky et al., 2022), and UNESCO's AI Competencies Framework (2024). Tenberga and Daniela's framework uniquely integrates both technical competencies and critical dimensions, such as ethics, communication, and awareness, that directly address teachers' roles and responsibilities. Its six interrelated components comprehensively cover the skills teachers need not only to use AI tools effectively but also to engage critically and ethically with AI in educational settings. This explicit focus on practical application and pedagogical integration aligns closely with the project's objectives, making it the most suitable framework for guiding the analysis and development of the AI literacy tools and recommendations presented.

Understanding the Fundamentals of AI refers to grasping the basic concepts of AI and how it functions in real-world applications. This dimension is measured through Questions 3, 6, and 13, which evaluate participants' knowledge of key concepts such as algorithms and machine learning processes.

Critical Evaluation of AI involves the ability to thoughtfully assess AI tools and their broader implications. Questions 4, 9, 12, and 14 address participants' competence in analysing AI outputs, recognising potential biases, and reflecting on the limitations and impacts of AI technologies.

Ethics focuses on moral considerations surrounding AI use. Questions 18, 19, and 20 assess respondents' awareness of issues such as data privacy, algorithmic bias, and accountability in automated systems.

Usage captures the practical dimension of AI literacy, examining individuals' ability to interact with and apply AI tools. Questions 1, 2, 7, 8, 11, 15, and 17 gauge the frequency and confidence with which participants use AI technologies in their teaching practices.

Awareness encompasses an understanding of AI's broader societal influence. This is addressed in Questions 5, 10, 21, 22, 23, and 25, which evaluate participants' awareness of AI-related trends, public discourse, and the role of AI in everyday life.

Communication reflects the ability to discuss and explain AI-related topics. Questions 16 and 24 assess how effectively individuals can articulate AI concepts and engage in informed conversations about AI.

These six components form a clear framework for evaluating AI literacy and understanding how teachers engage with GenAI tools. By integrating this framework into the design of the questionnaire, the study ensures alignment between theoretical constructs and empirical measures, ultimately supporting the development of an evidence-based AI literacy framework tailored to educational needs.

Table 1 presents the six components of the AI literacy framework developed by Tenberga and Daniela (2024), mapping each one, understanding, evaluation, ethics, usage, awareness, and communication, to the specific questionnaire items designed to assess participants' competencies in those areas.

Table 1 Components of AI-Literacy Framework

Component	Focus	Questionnaire items
Understanding	Basic AI concepts and how they work	Q3, Q6, Q13
Critical evaluation	Analysing outputs, identifying bias and limitations	Q4, Q9, Q12, Q14
Ethics	Awareness of privacy, fairness, and accountability	Q18, Q19, Q20
Usage	Practical application of AI tools in teaching	Q1, Q2, Q7, Q8, Q11, Q15, Q17
Awareness	Broader social, cultural, and educational implications	Q5, Q10, Q21, Q22, Q23, Q25
Communication	Ability to explain and discuss AI	Q16, Q24

The level of respondents' AI literacy was further explored through the analysis of responses to three open-ended questions, including Q26 (What successful uses of GenAI in your teaching did you experience or plan to use?) Q27 (What challenges or concerns do you face when using GenAI in your current or future teaching?) and Q28 (What types of professional development or support would help you feel more confident using GenAI in your classroom?)

Responses from both pre-service and in-service teachers across participating countries were analysed using an English-language ChatGPT prompt, aimed at assessing the extent to which their reflections aligned with the six AI literacy categories proposed by Tenberga & Daniela (2024).

2.2 AI LITERACY FROM THE LENS OF PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS

The questionnaire was completed by 473 pre-service teachers from four countries: Slovakia (n = 151; 31.9%), Latvia (n = 150; 31.7%), the Czech Republic (n = 115; 24.3%), and Israel (n = 57; 12.1%). This section first provides an overview of the participants' demographic characteristics, including their gender distribution, age, achieved education level, teaching experience, and teaching subjects. In addition, it presents data on the use of GenAI tools among the respondents. Following the demographic overview, the section summarises the key findings from the questionnaire, focusing on pre-service teachers' self-assessed AI literacy across six components defined in the framework by Tenberga and Daniela (2024): (1) understanding the fundamentals of AI, (2) critical evaluation of AI, (3) ethics, (4) usage, (5) awareness, and (6) communication.

2.2.1 Demographic Characteristics

Graph 1 Pre-service Teachers Respondents in four countries (N = 473, total number)

Graph 2 Pre-service Teachers Respondents: Representation of female in the sample in each country (N = 473, total number)

Across all participants, 63.6% were female (n = 301), with the proportion of female participants being 61.4% in Israel (n = 35), 71.3% in the Czech Republic (n = 82), 64.7% in Latvia (n = 97), and 57.6% in Slovakia (n = 87). In terms of age, the average age varied across countries: Israel had the oldest group (31.2 years), followed by Latvia (26.4), Slovakia (24.5), and the Czech Republic (23.5). Median ages ranged from 21.0 to 25.5 years, and maximum ages ranged from 51 to 58 years.

Graph 3 Pre-service Teachers: Achieved education (N = 473, total number)

In terms of educational attainment, among all participants, 45.2% (n = 214) held a Bachelor's degree, 35.1% (n = 166) had a Master's degree, and 29.8% (n = 141) were already qualified teachers.

In Israel, 70.2% ($n = 40$) held a Bachelor's degree, and 8.8% ($n = 5$) had a Master's degree. A total of 36.8% ($n = 21$) were already qualified teachers. Interestingly, the maximum teaching experience reported by Israeli participants was 0 years, indicating that although some held formal teaching qualifications, they likely had no classroom experience at the time of the study. The average teaching experience in Israel was 2.7 years.

From the Czech Republic, 24.3% ($n = 28$) had a Bachelor's degree, and 6.1% ($n = 7$) held a Master's degree. 16.5% ($n = 19$) were qualified teachers. The Czech participants reported an average of 1.6 years of teaching experience, with a maximum of 13 years.

In Latvia, the majority held a Bachelor's degree (76.0%; $n = 114$), while 24.0% ($n = 36$) had a Master's degree. A smaller portion, 14.0% ($n = 21$), were already qualified teachers. Latvian participants had an average of 2.5 years of teaching experience and the longest maximum experience among all countries at 18 years.

In Slovakia, 21.2% ($n = 32$) had a Bachelor's degree, while 78.1% ($n = 118$) held a Master's degree. More than half, 53.0% ($n = 80$), were already qualified teachers. Despite the high level of qualification, the average teaching experience among Slovak participants was only 0.7 years, with a maximum of 13 years.

This data highlights meaningful cross-country differences in pre-service teachers' education and experience. While Slovakia had the highest share of Master's degree holders and qualified teachers, its participants reported the least teaching experience. In contrast, Latvian participants were less often formally qualified but reported the highest levels of classroom experience.

Graph 4 Pre-service Teachers Respondents: Teaching subject (N = 473, total number)

Graph 5 Pre-service Teachers Respondents: Teaching subjects (N = 473, total number)

Participants represented a diverse range of teaching subjects. Science was the most commonly reported subject, particularly in Israel (38.6%; n = 22) and Slovakia (31.1%; n = 47). Math was also prominent, especially in Slovakia (25.8%; n = 39) and the Czech Republic (13.9%; n = 16). Languages were frequently selected in the Czech Republic (23.5%; n = 27) and Slovakia (23.2%; n = 35). Computing had strong representation in Slovakia (35.8%; n = 54) and the Czech Republic (20.9%; n = 24). Social Science was more evenly distributed, with Israel (12.3%; n = 7), Latvia (12.7%; n = 19), and the Czech Republic (11.3%; n = 13) showing similar levels. In contrast, Fine Art/Music, Sport, and Physical Education (PE) were less commonly reported, with little to no representation in Israel and smaller numbers in the other countries such as Fine Art/Music in the Czech Republic (7.8%; n = 9) and Sport in Latvia (13.3%; n = 20).

Graph 6 Pre-service Teachers' Experiences with GenAI tools (N = 473, total number)

Graph 7 Pre-service Teachers' Experiences with GenAI tools (N = 473, total number)

Most pre-service teachers reported using ChatGPT, with usage highest in the Czech Republic (97.4%; n = 112), followed by Latvia (94.7%; n = 142), Slovakia (93.4%; n = 141), and Israel (86.0%; n = 49). In total, 93.9% (n = 444) of participants had used ChatGPT. Gemini was used by 29.2% (n = 138) overall, with the highest usage in Slovakia (36.4%; n = 55) and Israel (31.6%; n = 18). Copilot was used by 24.9% (n = 118) of participants, most notably in Slovakia (28.5%; n = 43) and the Czech Republic (27.0%; n = 31). Claude had lower overall usage (12.1%; n = 57), with Israel (36.8%; n = 21) reporting the highest usage, followed by Latvia (15.3%; n = 23). MidJourney, used mainly for image generation, was reported by 12.5% (n = 59) overall, with the highest usage in the Czech Republic (16.5%; n = 19) and Slovakia (14.6%; n = 22). Other tools were mentioned by 6.1% (n = 29) of participants, with the highest share in Slovakia (8.6%; n = 13). Only 2.1% (n = 10) of participants reported not using any AI tools, with non-users in Slovakia (4.6%; n = 7) and the Czech Republic (2.6%; n = 3). No non-users were reported in Israel or Latvia.

2.2.2 Key findings

Graph 8 Key findings from the questionnaire (pre-service teachers, Q1-Q25, N = 473)

Note. 25 closed-ended questions measured on a 5-point Likert scale (1= strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree)

Among the four countries, **Latvia** scored the highest overall. Latvian students felt especially confident in understanding AI (3.64), using AI (3.71), and communicating about AI (3.71), showing both strong knowledge and practical skills.

Slovak respondents also rated themselves positively, particularly in critical thinking (3.71) and ethics (3.72). However, they scored lower in communication (2.93), suggesting they may need more support in expressing AI-related ideas.

The Czech Republic stood out for its strong focus on ethics (3.90) - the highest score across all countries and categories. They also did well in critical evaluation (3.59), but scored lowest in understanding AI (2.80), indicating a need for better foundational knowledge.

Israeli respondents had the lowest overall scores, though they showed relatively high confidence in ethics (3.80). Their lower ratings in understanding (3.04) and communication (2.73) may indicate not only lower perceived familiarity with AI concepts, but also a more self-critical self-assessment, potentially reflecting higher internal standards when evaluating their own competencies.

In summary, students across countries generally felt strongest in ethics and critical thinking, while communication and basic understanding were weaker in some contexts. These findings highlight the need to teach all six areas of AI literacy in teacher education programmes to fully prepare future educators for working with AI in schools.

In conclusion, the data reveal clear cross-country differences in self-perceived AI literacy among pre-service teachers. Ethical awareness and critical evaluation tend to be the strongest areas, whereas communication skills and foundational understanding show more

variability and are comparatively weaker in some contexts. These insights highlight the importance of incorporating all six components of AI literacy into teacher education curricula to ensure comprehensive preparation for teaching and interacting with AI in educational settings.

Open-ended responses (Q26, Q27 and Q28) provided important insights into the experiences, perceptions, and concerns of pre-service teachers regarding the use of GenAI in education. These responses, collected from participants in the Czech Republic, Slovakia, Israel, and Latvia, were analysed using the six-component AI literacy framework developed by Tenberga and Daniela (2024).

Understanding

Most pre-service teachers reported using GenAI for practical tasks such as lesson planning, creating exercises, adapting materials, and making presentations. This shows a basic functional understanding of GenAI tools. Some examples include generating grammar exercises, comparing student work with AI-generated versions, and developing ideas for critical thinking activities. However, many responses indicate a limited understanding of how GenAI works, such as how models are trained or how biases occur in data. This highlights a need for more training in the technical foundations of AI.

Evaluation

Many respondents showed the ability to critically assess AI-generated outputs. They mentioned checking the accuracy of content, comparing it with reliable sources, and using GenAI to support formative assessment. While some felt confident identifying errors in AI-generated material, most focused on immediate usefulness rather than deeper issues like bias or misinformation. There was little discussion about the limitations of AI systems or the broader impact of relying on them.

Ethics

Pre-service teachers expressed awareness of ethical concerns such as plagiarism, student misuse, data privacy, and the risk of over-reliance on GenAI. Some suggested banning GenAI in certain cases, while others called for teaching responsible use. Slovak participants highlighted the importance of discussing ethical and practical issues with students. A few respondents also raised concerns about the environmental costs of AI. However, broader ethical topics like algorithmic fairness or digital inclusion were mentioned less often.

Usage

Most respondents had already used GenAI in their teacher training or practice. Common uses included creating lesson plans, designing activities and assessments, and generating teaching materials. Some described using GenAI to support creativity, develop personalised resources, or assist with coding tasks. While these examples show active use, there was little focus on teaching students about how AI works or how to use it responsibly.

Awareness

Many pre-service teachers recognized that GenAI is likely to have a strong influence on the future of education. Some were optimistic, while others were cautious or unsure due to limited training. Czech respondents often reported curiosity but lacked practical experience. Israeli respondents discussed concerns about whether AI might reduce the need for certain teaching skills. Slovak participants reflected on how GenAI could change the teacher's role. Latvian teachers mentioned the risk of AI increasing educational inequality. However, few addressed wider issues like the labor market or AI governance.

Communication

Many respondents used GenAI to support language learning, create materials for class discussion, or write messages to parents. Activities included generating discussion prompts, role-playing with AI, and using AI to help students revise their writing. Some teachers discussed AI's risks and limitations with students, but others felt unprepared to explain these topics clearly. In Israel and Slovakia, several respondents noted that students may already be more skilled with AI than their teachers, pointing to a need for stronger communication skills and confidence among educators.

2.3 AI LITERACY FROM THE LENS OF IN-SERVICE TEACHERS

The questionnaire was completed by 562 in-service teachers from four countries: Israel (n = 175; 31.1%), the Czech Republic (n = 115; 20.5%), Latvia (n = 119; 21.2%), and Slovakia (n = 153; 27.2%). This section first provides an overview of the participants' demographic characteristics, including their gender distribution, age, achieved education level, teaching experience, and teaching subjects. In addition, it presents data on the use of generative AI tools among the respondents. Following the demographic overview, the section summarises the key findings from the questionnaire, focusing on in-service teachers' self-assessed AI literacy

across six components defined in the framework by Tenberga and Daniela (2024): (1) understanding the fundamentals of AI, (2) critical evaluation of AI, (3) ethics, (4) usage, (5) awareness, and (6) communication.

2.3.1 Demographic Characteristics

Graph 9 In-service Teachers Respondents in four countries (N = 562, total number)

Graph 10 In-service Teachers Respondents: Representation of female in the sample in each country (N = 562, total number)

In the total sample of 562 respondents, there were 175 in-service teachers from Israel (31.1%), 153 from Slovakia (27.2%), 115 from the Czech Republic (20.5%), and 119 from Latvia (21.2%). Of the total sample, 71.0% (n = 399) were female. The highest proportion of female participants was observed in Israel (75.4%; n = 132), followed by both the Czech

Republic (74.8%; n = 86) and Latvia (74.8%; n = 89), while Slovakia had the lowest proportion of female respondents (60.1%; n = 92).

In terms of age, the average age of participants ranged from 40.5 years in Latvia to 46.4 years in Israel. The median ages were close to the averages: 47 years in Israel, 46 in Slovakia, 42 in the Czech Republic, and 41 in Latvia.

Across all four countries, the sample also included older educators, reflecting the continued participation of senior teachers in the profession. The oldest respondents were aged 74 in Israel, 71 in the Czech Republic, 66 in Slovakia, and 63 in Latvia.

Graph 11 In-service Teachers: Achieved education (N = 562, total number)

Overall, 67.1% (n = 377) of the participants held a Master's degree, 25.1% (n = 141) held a Bachelor's degree, and 91.3% (n = 513) were already qualified teachers. Among teachers from Israel (n = 175), 35.4% (n = 62) had a Bachelor's degree, 58.3% (n = 102) held a Master's degree, and 93.7% (n = 164) were qualified. In the Czech Republic (n = 115), only 5.2% (n = 6) held a Bachelor's degree, while 75.7% (n = 87) had completed a Master's degree; 73.9% (n = 85) were qualified teachers. In Latvia (n = 119), 53.8% (n = 64) had a Bachelor's degree, 38.7% (n = 46) a Master's degree, and all participants (100%; n = 119) were qualified. Among teachers from Slovakia (n = 153), 5.9% (n = 9) had a Bachelor's degree, while 92.8% (n = 142) held a Master's degree, and 94.8% (n = 145) were qualified.

In terms of teaching experience, the average years ranged from 13.5 years in Latvia to 16.4 years in Slovakia. Median years of experience were highest in Slovakia (16 years) and

Israel (14 years), while maximum reported teaching experience ranged from 37 years in Latvia to 56 years in Slovakia.

Graph 12 In-service Teachers Respondents: Teaching subject (N = 562, total number)

Graph 13 In-service Teachers Respondents: Teaching subject (N = 562, total number)

Graphs 12 and 13 present the distribution of teaching subjects among in-service teachers (N = 562) from Israel, the Czech Republic, Latvia, and Slovakia. The data reveal notable differences in subject focus across the four countries.

In Israel (n = 70), the most commonly taught subject is Science (36.0%, n = 25), followed by Languages (21.1%, n = 15) and Maths (20.0%, n = 14). Other subjects include Social Science (10.9%, n = 8), Computing (2.9%, n = 2), Fine Art/Music (1.7%, n = 1), and Sport (1.7%, n = 1). No teachers reported teaching Physical Education (PE).

In the Czech Republic (n = 71), there is a more balanced distribution. Computing is the most common subject (34.8%, n = 25), followed by Maths (30.4%, n = 22), Science (28.7%, n = 20), and Languages (24.3%, n = 17). Fine Art/Music (24.3%, n = 17) and Social Science (24.3%, n = 17) are also well represented. PE (12.2%, n = 9) and Sport (11.3%, n = 8) appear more frequently here than in the other countries.

In Latvia (n = 118), the dominant subject by far is Languages (52.9%, n = 62). Other subjects include Maths (13.4%, n = 16), Social Science (7.6%, n = 9), Science (5.9%, n = 7), Computing (5.9%, n = 7), and PE (11.8%, n = 14). Very few teachers are involved in Sport (0.8%, n = 1), and none reported teaching Fine Art/Music.

In Slovakia (n = 303), Science (46.4%, n = 141) and Computing (46.4%, n = 141) are the most frequently taught subjects, followed by Maths (40.5%, n = 123) and Languages (28.1%, n = 85). Fine Art/Music and Social Science are each taught by 7.2% of respondents (n = 22), while Sport (4.6%, n = 14) and PE (1.3%, n = 4) are less common.

Looking at the overall distribution (N = 562) across all four countries, the most frequently taught subjects are Science (31.0%, n = 174), Languages (30.4%, n = 171), and Maths (26.3%, n = 148). These are followed by Computing (21.9%, n = 123), Social Science (11.9%, n = 67), Fine Art/Music (7.5%, n = 42), PE (5.3%, n = 30), and Sport (4.3%, n = 24).

These results suggest that while Science, Maths, and Languages are key focus areas in all countries, there are significant variations in the emphasis placed on other subjects, reflecting national differences in curriculum priorities and teacher specialisation.

Graph 14 In-service Teachers' Experiences with GenAI tools (N = 562, total number)

Graph 15 In-service Teachers' Experiences with GenAI tools (N = 562, total number)

Graphs 14 and 15 show the use of generative AI tools among 562 in-service teachers across Israel, the Czech Republic, Latvia, and Slovakia. ChatGPT is the most widely used tool overall, with 87.5% of teachers (n = 492) reporting its use. Usage is especially high in Latvia (95.0%, n = 112), the Czech Republic (87.0%, n = 62), and Slovakia (86.3%, n = 261), while it is notably lower in Israel (26.2%, n = 18). Other tools like Gemini (37.5%, n = 211), Copilot (29.0%, n = 163), and Claude (21.2%, n = 119) are used to a lesser extent, with varying popularity across countries. MidJourney and other tools have relatively low usage overall. A small proportion of teachers reported not using any AI tools, most notably in Slovakia (11.1%, n = 34) and the Czech Republic (6.1%, n = 4), while none reported non-use in Latvia or Israel.

2.3.2 Key Findings

Graph 16 Key findings from the questionnaire (in-service teachers, Q1-Q25, N = 562)

Note. 25 closed-ended questions measured on a 5-point Likert scale (1= strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree)

Latvian teachers scored the highest overall, especially in critical evaluation of AI (3.71), ethics (3.61), and communication (3.58), suggesting strong confidence in understanding, using, and discussing AI in education.

Czech teachers reported the highest score of all countries in AI ethics (3.92), along with strong results in critical evaluation (3.55) and awareness (3.56). However, they showed lower confidence in basic understanding (2.82) and usage (3.04), indicating a more reflective than practical orientation.

Israeli teachers had moderate scores, with the highest in AI awareness (3.67). Yet, they reported lower confidence in using AI (2.87) and communicating about it (2.68), pointing to limited hands-on experience.

Slovak teachers scored the lowest overall, especially in understanding (2.61), usage (2.67), and communication (2.70). Their best score was in awareness (3.49), suggesting general familiarity with AI trends but limited practical knowledge.

Overall, while teachers from different countries are generally aware of AI and its ethical issues, many do not feel confident using it, understanding how it works, or talking about it. This shows that teacher education programmes need to offer more training focused on AI.

Responses from in-service teachers to Q26, Q27 and Q28 were analysed using the AI literacy framework developed by Tenberga and Daniela (2024). Compared to pre-service teachers, in-service teachers showed a stronger focus on the implications of GenAI for student learning and expressed greater concern about responsible and ethical use. Many responses reflect a cautious but growing engagement with GenAI, shaped by classroom realities and professional responsibilities.

Understanding

Some in-service teachers use GenAI for tasks such as lesson planning, curriculum review, test creation, and coding support. However, many report limited understanding of how GenAI works. Non-STEM teachers, in particular, express a lack of foundational knowledge about machine learning and AI principles. Despite this, there is interest in learning how to prompt GenAI tools effectively. Some Slovak respondents believe AI can help explain complex topics to young learners, while Latvian teachers report efforts to teach students how to use GenAI through activities like citation and prompt-writing workshops. Teachers also highlight the limitations of GenAI in providing nuanced, context-aware responses.

Evaluation

Many in-service teachers demonstrate critical evaluation by comparing AI-generated materials with their own and encouraging students to verify AI content. AI is used in media literacy lessons to help students distinguish reliable from false information. Concerns about reliability, accuracy, and bias are common. Some Israeli respondents note that GenAI often produces generic or incorrect content in subjects like literature. Latvian teachers mention the difficulty of identifying when students have used AI appropriately, pointing to a need for clearer evaluation criteria.

Ethics

Ethical concerns are prominent in the responses. Teachers worry about plagiarism, academic dishonesty, and the erosion of essential student skills like critical thinking and writing. Data privacy and the lack of clear guidelines are major concerns. Latvian teachers, for example, limit AI use to approved platforms to protect student data. Some also use AI-related bias examples as learning opportunities to foster ethical awareness.

Usage

In-service teachers provided a wide range of practical examples of GenAI use: lesson planning, differentiated quiz generation, worksheet and image creation, group learning activities, music production, information retrieval, summarising content, and giving feedback. Latvian teachers are experimenting with AI-assisted grading and co-creating prompts with students. Compared to pre-service teachers, their use is more diversified and integrated into everyday teaching.

Awareness

Czech and Israeli teachers show awareness of AI's influence on education and the labour market. Some worry that education systems are not keeping pace with AI developments. Teachers in Slovakia emphasise AI's role in supporting individualised learning, while Latvian teachers are concerned about unequal access to AI benefits, with tech-savvy students gaining more. Fear that GenAI might replace human cognitive functions is also present among respondents.

Communication

Some in service teachers collaborate on AI projects and share best practices, particularly in the Czech Republic. However, many still struggle to explain AI clearly to students and parents. Israeli teachers report mixed experiences. Some actively discuss AI with students, while others lack the confidence or training to do so effectively. Latvian teachers are working to strengthen communication about AI, using peer review and class discussions to address misconceptions and build understanding.

2.4 INSIGHTS FROM TEACHER EDUCATORS AND PARENTS

2.4.1 Parents' Perspectives Analysed by the Six-Component AI Literacy Framework Understanding the Fundamentals of AI

Most parents demonstrated a general awareness of GenAI tools such as ChatGPT, with varying levels of understanding of how these technologies function. While some parents, particularly those with technical or IT-related backgrounds, were familiar with the concepts of prompts and AI-generated responses, others had only recently encountered GenAI or had not used it personally. Their understanding was largely shaped by everyday use cases or what they observed in their children's learning activities.

Critical Evaluation of AI

Parents expressed concerns about the credibility and reliability of AI-generated content. Many were aware that GenAI tools can produce inaccurate or misleading information and discussed the importance of teaching children to critically evaluate what AI produces. Some parents worried that overreliance on AI might lead to diminished critical thinking skills and passive consumption of information.

Ethics

Ethical concerns emerged as a strong theme across all parent groups. Parents emphasised the importance of data protection, the potential for misuse of AI in schoolwork, and the need for children to develop a responsible and ethical approach to technology use. There were concerns about fairness in education and the risk of exacerbating inequalities if only some pupils had access to AI-supported learning tools.

Usage

Parental usage of GenAI varied considerably. Some parents used GenAI regularly for work-related writing, planning, or household tasks. Others had not yet used these tools at all. Interestingly, many parents noted that their children were ahead of them in using GenAI, particularly for completing homework. Parents' confidence in using AI themselves was generally lower than their children's, reinforcing the need for support and digital education at the family level.

Awareness

Although most parents were not fully (in the case of Czech or Slovak parents, not at all) informed about national or school-level policy developments on GenAI, there was a strong sense of growing awareness. Parents recognised that AI would play a major role in their children's future and expressed interest in learning more. Some were concerned about the lack of structured conversations between schools and families regarding the responsible use of GenAI in education.

Communication

The ability of parents to communicate with their children about AI-related issues varied. While some parents engaged in discussions about GenAI and even collaborated with their children in using it, many admitted they lacked the vocabulary or knowledge to do so meaningfully. This communication gap highlighted the importance of providing resources to parents, enabling them to support and guide their children's use of AI.

2.4.2 Teacher Educators' Perspectives Analysed by the Six-Component AI Literacy Framework

Understanding the Fundamentals of AI

Teacher educators generally exhibited a higher level of understanding of AI fundamentals compared to parents. Many could explain how GenAI tools function, including basic concepts such as machine learning and algorithmic processing. Israeli and Czech participants, in particular, demonstrated deeper technical understanding, though others from Latvia and Slovakia called for more training to build foundational knowledge.

Critical Evaluation of AI

There was broad consensus among teacher educators about the importance of evaluating AI outputs critically. Many participants discussed AI's limitations, such as biased responses or fabricated information, and recognised the need to develop pupils' skills in assessing the reliability and accuracy of content generated by AI tools.

Ethics

Ethical considerations were central to the teacher educators' discussions. Concerns included data privacy, the lack of transparency in algorithmic decision-making, and the appropriate boundaries of AI use in teaching and assessment. Participants called for ethics to be a core part of teacher training and classroom instruction, ensuring that both teachers and learners approach AI use with responsibility and care.

Usage

Teacher educators reported varied levels of practical engagement with GenAI tools. Some used AI regularly in designing learning materials, assessments, or professional tasks, while others were still in the early stages of exploration. Those with prior digital training or involvement in innovation projects felt more confident in experimenting with GenAI, whereas others expressed hesitation due to a lack of structured support.

Awareness

Most teacher educators were aware of the broader implications of AI for education and society, especially those from Israel and the Czech Republic. They followed global discussions about AI in education and reflected on how these debates shaped their own practices. However, others, particularly in Slovakia and Latvia, indicated that policy guidance and institutional support remained limited, which constrained their engagement with AI developments.

Communication

The ability to communicate AI-related concepts effectively varied across teacher educators. Some felt confident discussing AI in professional settings and with pupils, often facilitating critical conversations in teacher training programmes. Others struggled with explaining AI in accessible terms, indicating a need for professional development focused on communication and pedagogical framing of GenAI in education.

2.4.3 Conclusion

The research results demonstrate both the current capabilities and boundaries of GenAI literacy among parents and teacher educators. The educational significance of AI has become more widely recognised but this awareness does not translate to consistent understanding or ethical readiness or confident implementation. Parents base their understanding on observations and personal experiences but they trail their children in both technology usage and critical thinking abilities. The teacher educators demonstrate advanced theoretical knowledge and classroom implementation skills yet they encounter institutional obstacles including limited training opportunities and insufficient support from their institutions and ambiguous policy frameworks. Both groups require specific professional development together with inclusive dialogue and systemic approaches which extend past enthusiastic isolated practice. The successful implementation of GenAI in school education requires stakeholders to develop capabilities that extend beyond technology usage to questioning and adapting and leading its application through pedagogically sound and ethically robust methods.

Chapter Conclusions

This chapter developed an evidence based AI literacy framework to support pre service and in service teachers in integrating GenAI into core teaching work, including planning, instruction, assessment, and the creation of learning materials. Anchored in Tenberga and Daniela's six component model and informed by survey and focus group evidence across four countries, the chapter shows that GenAI adoption is already widespread, yet readiness remains uneven and often partial.

Across contexts, teachers report the strongest confidence in ethical awareness and critical evaluation, but these strengths are not consistently translated into classroom routines, assessment design, or clear guidance for learners. Foundational understanding of how GenAI works, how bias and hallucination arise, and what data practices are implicated remains variable, especially outside STEM related backgrounds. Communication is a recurring weak point, not only in explaining AI to learners and parents, but also in setting transparent norms for acknowledgement, acceptable use, and the purposes for which GenAI support is appropriate. These gaps appear in both pre service and in service groups, suggesting that exposure to tools alone does not develop durable professional competence.

The qualitative evidence clarifies why. In service teachers engage with GenAI through the pressures of real classrooms, which makes their use more varied and situated, but also

intensifies concerns about academic integrity, reliability, privacy, and fairness. Pre service teachers show high levels of tool use for immediate instructional tasks, yet their reflections indicate limited conceptual depth and a tendency to frame evaluation narrowly as quick accuracy checking rather than sustained reasoning about limitations, bias, or epistemic risk. Teacher educators demonstrate stronger theoretical orientation and greater sensitivity to ethics and pedagogy, but they describe institutional constraints, uneven professional learning opportunities, and unclear policy signals. Parents recognise the significance of AI for their children's futures but often lack the language and confidence to discuss GenAI meaningfully, and many perceive that children are already outpacing adults in use.

Taken together, the findings indicate that AI literacy cannot be treated as an optional add on or a short term training topic. It requires a coherent progression that starts with foundations and ethical reasoning, then moves to pedagogical design, assessment and feedback practices, and finally to communication and partnership with families. It also requires alignment across levels, national guidance, institutional policies, and classroom practice, so that expectations for AI use are consistent, teachable, and equitable. Without this alignment, responsibility is pushed onto individual teachers, widening disparities between schools, subjects, and learners.

The framework therefore positions teachers not only as users of GenAI but as professional decision makers who shape when, why, and how GenAI is used in ways that protect learning, integrity, and inclusion. Building this capacity demands sustained professional learning, clear norms for acknowledgement and assessment, and practical resources that model responsible GenAI use in specific subjects and age groups. With these supports in place, GenAI can be integrated as a tool that strengthens human centred education rather than weakening it, and teachers can lead the shift from experimentation toward trustworthy and pedagogically grounded practice.

CONCLUSION

This volume illustrates how AI in education represents a landscape where technological progress coexists with uneven access and readiness. Despite the ambitious objectives of the AI-EmpaTe project, systemic, pedagogical, and ethical complexities continue to hinder widespread adoption. A central challenge lies in the disconnect between the ambitions of national strategies and the actual capabilities at the local level, particularly in relation to teacher training, curriculum development, and institutional preparedness.

Latvia and Israel exemplify effective planning and coherent policy implementation. In Latvia, strong collaboration between government agencies, universities, and schools ensures that AI education is integrated across all stages of the system. The Czech Republic, by contrast, demonstrates how academic leadership and grassroots innovation can drive progress even in the absence of timely central directives. Slovakia is currently advancing its digital education agenda while participating in the ICILS international assessment programme to strengthen the evaluation of digital competencies. Although national AI strategies continue to evolve, Slovak educators and researchers are increasingly engaged in EU-supported initiatives that aim to foster cross-sectoral collaboration in AI integration.

Teacher preparedness emerges as a critical concern across all research contexts. While awareness of AI's potential is steadily growing, investment in teacher education, both pre-service and in-service, remains insufficient to address the full range of benefits and risks associated with AI in the classroom. Without robust, ongoing professional development, AI use in education is likely to remain superficial, failing to translate into meaningful pedagogical transformation.

The rapid development of generative AI tools has created an urgent need for strategic action. Although these technologies offer opportunities for personalised learning and instructional efficiency, they also introduce complex challenges related to bias, transparency, and the safeguarding of critical thinking. Ethical frameworks, though widely endorsed at the institutional level, are inconsistently implemented across educational settings.

Effective AI integration requires far more than access to technology; it calls for a fundamental cultural shift that prioritises interdisciplinary collaboration, inclusive policy making, and a commitment to human-centred education. AI should not be seen merely as a tool for automating existing processes but as a catalyst for reimagining teaching and learning. The AI-EmpaTe project contributes significantly to this transformative agenda. However, systemic

success will ultimately depend on sustained engagement from all stakeholders, grounded in ethical responsibility, educational equity, and a shared vision for the future of learning.

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APPENDICES

Appendix A - Survey for Pre-Service and In-Service Teachers

Teachers' Needs and Perspectives on GenAI in Teaching and Learning

Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) refers to systems such as ChatGPT, Claude, Copilot, Gemini, Midjourney, and many others that generate new content like text, images, and code based on patterns learned from vast amounts of data.

This survey aims to assess teachers' needs and perspectives regarding the use of GenAI in educational settings. It touches on key areas such as preparation, in-class use, and feedback, as well as the importance of ethical use and capacity-building for teachers.

Thank you for taking the time to answer this questionnaire and participate in our research.

The questionnaire is anonymous and respondents cannot be identified. Your information will not be shared with anyone outside of the research team. Completing the questionnaire should take approximately 20 minutes.

There are no wrong answers, so please feel free to answer honestly!

Demographics

- Gender:
 - Male Female Other
- Age: _____
- Education:
 - Secondary education BA degree MA degree (teacher education)
 - MA degree (other) PhD degree
- Teacher Qualification: Yes No
- Years of teaching experience: _____
- Teaching subject:
 - Science Math Art & Music Social Studies Language Other: _____
- Level of education where I teach:
 - Primary Secondary Higher education Other
- GenAI tools you used (select all that apply):
 - ChatGPT Copilot Claude Gemini MidJourney Others: _____

Part 1: Before Teaching

Focus: Preparation and GenAI Literacy

Please rate your agreement (1–Strongly Disagree to 5–Strongly Agree)

1. I feel confident in my ability to use GenAI tools to enhance my teaching practices.
2. I use GenAI tools to plan and design engaging lesson materials.
3. I feel confident in developing or customising GenAI-based tools for teaching.

4. I can evaluate the content generated by GenAI tools for accuracy and appropriateness.
5. I am familiar with the applications of GenAI in personalised and adaptive learning.
6. I understand how GenAI works (e.g. training on large datasets, machine learning).

Part 2: During Teaching

Focus: Enhancing Classroom Learning with GenAI Tools

Please rate your agreement (1–Strongly Disagree to 5–Strongly Agree)

7. I use GenAI to provide real-time support to students.
8. I find GenAI tools help students engage more actively.
9. I can explain to students how to critically assess GenAI-generated content.
10. I believe GenAI promotes creativity and problem-solving among students.
11. I encourage students to use GenAI for self-regulated learning and research.
12. I am concerned about students becoming overly dependent on GenAI tools.
13. I can explain to students how GenAI works and how it differs from other AI types.
14. I can distinguish between students' personal work and GenAI-generated work

Part 3: After Teaching

Focus: Assessment and Feedback

Please rate your agreement (1–Strongly Disagree to 5–Strongly Agree)

15. GenAI assists me in analysing students' performance and giving personalised feedback.
16. I find GenAI helps streamline my assessment process while maintaining standards.
17. I use GenAI insights to adapt future lessons and strategies.

Part 4: Ethical and Responsible Use

Focus: Understanding and Mitigating Risks

Please rate your agreement (1–Strongly Disagree to 5–Strongly Agree)

18. I am aware of the ethical challenges of GenAI and take steps to mitigate them.
19. I teach students about the ethical responsibilities involved in using GenAI.
20. I am aware of institutional guidelines or policies on GenAI use.
21. I believe it is important to teach students to create content with GenAI, not just consume it.

Part 5: Teacher Professional Development

Focus: Building Teachers' GenAI Competency

Please rate your agreement (1–Strongly Disagree to 5–Strongly Agree)

22. Teachers should have knowledge and skills to guide students in GenAI use.
23. I am interested in professional development on using GenAI effectively.
24. My institution provides sufficient support and resources for GenAI integration.
25. I have experienced challenges in integrating GenAI into the curriculum.

Part 6: Open-ended Questions (Open-ended Questions)

26. What successful uses of GenAI in your teaching have you experienced or planned?
27. What challenges or concerns do you face when using GenAI? Have you found solutions?
28. What types of professional development would help you feel more confident using GenAI?

Appendix B - Focus Group Questions for Teacher Educators

Questions for focus groups with teacher educators were related to four topics:

Topic 1: Understanding (Gen)AI in Education//Experiences with GenAI

- Have you tried any tools using GenAI? (What specific tools or types of tools? In what situations or for what purposes? What fears or feelings did it leave in you?)
- Do you have any favorite GenAI tools?
- Do you use GenAI in your teaching? (What types or tools? What is the effectiveness or benefit?)

Topic 2: GenAI in Education

- What information do you have about using GenAI in education?
- Do you know any conceptual or complex solutions or specific use cases in this area?
- What is your opinion on the use of GenAI in teaching in general?
- What options and ways of involving GenAI in teaching can you think of? How do you feel about these options?
- Are you interested in whether the Ministry of Education, your university or other organisations (NPI, etc.) have issued or are issuing any guidelines for the use of GenAI in schools? (Are you aware of this?)

Topic 3: GenAI and teacher competency

- What knowledge, skills, and dispositions are essential for teachers to be able to use GenAI in teaching?
- What knowledge, skills, and dispositions are essential for teachers to navigate the evolving landscape of GenAI in education

Topic 4: Supporting teachers' professional development

- Do you have any experience with training teachers or student teachers in the use of GenAI?
- Do you consider any (potential) issues or concerns related to the use of GenAI in teacher education?

Appendix C- Focus Group Questions for Parents

Questions for focus groups with parents were focused on following four topics:

Topic 1: Understanding (Gen)AI in Education

- Have you tried any tools using GenAI?
- What specific tools or applications?
- In what situations or for what purposes?
- What concerns or feelings did it leave you with?
- Do you have any favorite GenAI tools?
- Are you positive (“enthusiastic”) or more concerned?
- Do you discuss AI issues with your children at home?
- Do you use AI with your children at home?

Topic 2: GenAI should used in schools

- How did you find out about it?
- Did the school/teachers hold any discussions with parents on this topic?)
- What do you think about the importance of GenAI for school results and skill development in children?
- Do you see it more positively or negatively?
- Will GenAI help or harm?
- Do you have any ideas about how teachers could or should use GenAI with children in their lessons?

Topic 3: GenAI in Curriculum and support

- Do you know whether the Ministry of Education or the Institution responsible for education in your country has issued or is issuing any guidelines for the use of GenAI in schools?
- Would you support the implementation of GenAI tools in the school curriculum?

Topic 4: Expectations/ The future of AI in Education

- What will be the future involvement of GenAI in the work of teachers?
- What will it look like with GenAI and education in general?
- What measures would you like to implement to ensure the responsible use of GenAI in education?